

Injustice by algorithm:

'Predictive' policing and criminal 'prediction' and profiling systems used by law enforcement and criminal justice authorities in Spain

AlgoRace

(Des)Racializando la IA

Author: Naiara Bellio

Collaborators: Ana Valdivia & Javier Sánchez Monedero

Traducción: Aurora Ali & Najim M. Ouled

Editors: Griff Ferris & Sofia Lyall

Design and layout: Isabel Muriedas

AlgoRace & Statewatch

Limitations

The research for this report was closed in December 2023. Due to organizational reasons, its publication was delayed until now. The information contained in it includes interviews and research conducted up to the end of 2023, and therefore does not contemplate further updates to the systems included in it or the adoption of new regulation.

In this line, the report does not assess the enforcement of the EU AI Act Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024.

Some of the systems included in the report could have also been updated since the research was conducted. For instance, VioGén was updated to a new version in early 2025; RisCanvi was audited in 2024; and VeriPol was shut down in late 2024. These modifications are not contemplated in the report.

Names of interviewees have been removed to avoid confusions due to the time limitations, as some of them are not currently in the role they had when interviewed in 2023.

Índex

Abbreviations	5
Definitions	7
Executive Summary	9
Introduction	12
Methodology	13
Transparency and obstruction	15
‘Predictive’ policing: Location-focused crime ‘prediction’ systems	16
Predictive Police Patrolling Decision Support System’ or ‘Smart patrolling’ (National Police)	17
EuroCop	19
DataWeb (Mossos d’Esquadra, Catalonia)	22
‘Predictive’ policing: Person-focused crime ‘prediction’, profiling and risk assessment systems	24
VioGén (National Police)	24
EPV-R (Ertzaintza, Basque Country & judiciary, Basque Country)	29
Profiling of sexual offenders (National Police)	34
VeriPol (National Police)	35
CAMINS (Mossos d’Esquadra, Catalonia)	38
Videosurveillance & image recognition systems (Community of Madrid)	40
Prisons: Person-focused ‘predictive’ and profiling systems	43
DRAVY (Spanish Penitentiary Institutions)	43
RisCanvi (Department of Justice, Catalonia)	47
Databases	51
a. ABIS (Automated Biometric Identification System database)	53
b. ADEXTTRA (Foreigner registration database)	54
c. ADPASFIL (Passports and migration database)	56
Conclusions	57

Abbreviations

Siglas	Término en inglés
ADM	Automated decision-making systems
AI	Artificial intelligence
AGI	Artificial general intelligence
P3-DSS	Predictive Police Patrolling Decision Support System
EPV-R	Intimate Partner Femicide and Severe Violence Assessment
ABIS	Automated Biometric Identification System (formerly SAID)
SAID	Automated System for Fingerprint Identification
ADEXTTRA	Foreigner registration database
ADPASFIL	Passports and migration database
EU AI Act	European Union Artificial Intelligence Act
FOIA	Freedom of Information Access
OSINT	Open source intelligence
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
VPR	Police Risk Assessment
VPER	Evolution of the Police Risk Assessment

EBA	Protection of Women and Households (digital platform in the Basque Country)
ANPR	Automated Number Plate Recognition
CCTV	Closed Circuit Television
DRAVY	Detection of violent jihadist radicalisation
LSIR	Level of Service Inventory-Revised
IFRS	INTERPOL's Face Recognition System
NIE	Foreigner Identification Number

Definitions

Artificial intelligence:

The European Union Artificial Intelligence Act defines an AI system as:

“...a machine-based system that is designed to operate with varying levels of autonomy and that may exhibit adaptiveness after deployment, and that, for explicit or implicit objectives, infers, from the input it receives, how to generate outputs such as predictions, content, recommendations, or decisions that can influence physical or virtual environments.”¹

This report uses this definition, though there are many ways to define AI and AI systems.² It is important to note that most of the data-based, algorithmic and automated systems used by police and criminal legal system authorities in Spain do not use artificial intelligence. Some of these systems use machine learning (see below), a sub-field of AI. However, the majority of these systems use classic statistical methods and can be described as automated-decision making systems (see below).

Machine learning:

The Cambridge Dictionary defines machine-learning as “the process of computers improving their own ability to carry out tasks by analysing new data, without a human needing to give instructions in the form of a program, or the study of creating and using computer systems that can do this”.³

Automated decision-making system:

The United Kingdom Office for AI defines automated decision-making systems as those which employ “solely automated decisions (no human judgement involved),” as well as “automated assisted decision-making (assisting human judgement).”⁴

Algorithm:

There is no universally accepted definition for an algorithm. A common definition states: “An algorithm is a set of rules that precisely define a sequence of operations.”⁵ Within the context of statistics and machine learning, this refers to the set of instructions a computer executes to learn from data.⁶

¹ Article 3(1), Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32024R1689#art_3

² To give just one example, the definition in the EU AI Act is substantially different from the one included in the initial proposal. See: ‘Proposal for a Regulation laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence’, 21 April 2021, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52021PC0206>

³ Cambridge Dictionary, ‘Machine learning’, <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/machine-learning>

⁴ Cabinet Office et al. (2021). Ethics, Transparency and Accountability Framework for Automated Decision-Making. GOV.UK.

⁵ Stone, Harold S. (1971), Introduction to Computer Organization and Data Structures, McGraw-Hill, Inc., USA.

⁶ MIT Technology Review (2021), “What is an ‘algorithm’? It depends on whom you ask”, 26 de febrero de 2021, disponible en: <https://www.technologyreview.com/2021/02/26/1020007/what-is-an-algorithm/>

Biometric data:

Biometric data is widely accepted as a category of “sensitive personal data”. The AI Now Institute states that: “most legal approaches to regulating biometrics adopt a narrow definition of the term that is conditional on the ability and use of the bodily information to confirm or establish a person’s official identity.”

However, these definitions do not account for other types of bodily information, that may not confirm a person’s identity but still reveal sensitive personal data, for example heart rate monitoring, perspiration, and gait tracking, among others.⁷

‘Predictive’ policing:

There are two main types of so-called predictive policing: location-focused, and person-focused. Amnesty International defines predictive policing systems as:

“...computer programs that use data and algorithmic models to assess the risk that a crime will be committed. Predictive policing systems calculate risk scores that allegedly reflect the likelihood that a person or group is or will be a victim or perpetrator [person-focused], or that a specific location will be a future crime scene [location-focused predictive policing]. Based on these computer-generated risk scores, the police take measures seeking to prevent or detect the predicted crime by directing policing efforts towards ‘high-risk’ locations, individuals, or groups.”

⁷ AI Now Institute (2023), "Biometric Surveillance Is Quietly Expanding: Bright-Line Rules Are Key", 11 de abril de 2023, disponible en: <https://ainowinstitute.org/publication/biometric-surveillance-is-quietly-expanding#footnote-25>

Executive summary

Across Spain, police and criminal legal system authorities have been introducing data-based, automated decision-making (ADM) and artificial intelligence (AI) systems to make and support decision-making in police forces and prisons.

These systems, which are often rapidly developed and implemented with little transparency or public disclosure, range from more advanced methods of computer analysis, sometimes drawing on AI and machine-learning, but often consist of basic methods of data analysis, and non-automated databases.

These systems influence real-life decisions and can lead to serious criminal legal system consequences, including police surveillance and monitoring, questioning, stop and search, fines, and harsher outcomes for sentencing, probation, immigration, and welfare decisions.

Predictive systems in policing and criminal legal settings disproportionately target and impact specific groups and communities, including women, migrants, racialised minorities and non-nationals or people from working-class backgrounds and individuals.

a. Key findings

This report covers some of the key automated decision-making (ADM) systems and databases that have previously or are currently used by police forces and prisons in Spain. For each system, the report provides information obtained on the system's purpose, data used, and impacts on people and places.

The first section of the report covers predictive systems developed by the Spanish police including: location-focused crime 'prediction' systems that allegedly 'predict' where and when a crime will take place; and person-focused crime 'prediction', profiling, and risk assessment systems that allegedly 'predict' the likelihood of future harm or violence from an individual.

The location-focused crime 'prediction' systems used by police that this report covers are:

- **Predictive Police Patrolling Decision Support System (P3-DSS)** and **EuroCop**. These are used to 'predict' crime in locations and identify crime 'hotspots', in order to allocate police patrols or target areas with more police. The Predictive Police Patrolling Decision Support System is used by the Spanish National Police and EuroCop is used by local police forces, currently deployed in seven regions across Spain. These systems rely on historical crime data, which often reflects existing structural biases within the criminal legal system, leading to over-policing of marginalised and racialised communities.
- **DataWeb**, used by the Mossos d'Esquadra in Catalonia, relies on crime data to locate possible crimes.

The person-focused crime prediction, profiling and risk assessment systems used by police that this report covers are:

- **VioGén**, a gender-based violence risk assessment system used by the Spanish National Police, evaluates the risk of reoffending by alleged perpetrators. Despite its widespread use, concerns have been raised about its accuracy and potential for bias, particularly against migrant women.
- **EPV-R**, used by the Ertzaintza in the Basque Country, assesses the risk of severe partner violence. The system has been criticised for its use of subjective criteria, including the nationality of the offender, which can lead to discriminatory outcomes.
- **VeriPol**, a system used to detect false crime reports, analyses the language of police reports to identify potential fraud. However, its use of police crime report data, and influence of police assessments, may reproduce societal biases, particularly against non-native Spanish speakers.

The second section of the report covers two 'predictive' systems used in Spanish prisons, both of which are person-focused crime prediction, profiling, and risk assessment systems:

- **DRAVY**, used by Spanish Penitentiary Institutions, profiles prisoners at risk of so-called "jihadist radicalization." The system has a high rate of false positives, leading to stricter prison conditions for individuals who may not pose a real threat. It disproportionately targets Muslim prisoners, particularly those of Moroccan descent.
- **RisCanvi**, used in Catalan prisons, assesses the risk of re-offending (recidivism) among inmates. While it is used to inform parole and probation decisions, it has been criticized for its lack of transparency and potential bias against non-Spanish nationals.

The third section of the report offers an overview of three main police databases in Spain holding vast swathes of sensitive data about marginalised groups, including migrants, and detainees. These databases are accessed by police to support decision-making, and are sometimes used to supply training datasets for algorithmic crime 'prediction' systems:

- **ABIS**, a biometric identification system, stores fingerprints and facial images of detainees and suspects. It is used for criminal investigations, but raises concerns about privacy and the potential for misidentification.
- **ADEXTTRA** and **ADPASFIL** are databases used to manage information on migrants, including biometric data and immigration status. These systems are often poorly updated, leading to wrongful detentions and deportations of individuals with legal status.

b) Key issues

The use of data-based, ADM and AI systems by police and criminal legal system authorities raises serious concerns, with significant consequences for individuals' rights, including the right to a fair trial, privacy, and freedom from discrimination. The analysis in this report addresses the following issues:

- **Criminalisation:** Crime 'prediction' systems label people and places as criminal. Location-focused systems in Spain, such as P3-DSS and EuroCop, direct police to target so-called crime 'hotspots'. Person-focused or individual risk assessment systems in Spain, such as VioGén and RisCanvi, label individuals as potentially criminal or violent. These systems result in people in those areas and subject to those profiles being more likely to be criminalised as a result, as well as facing harsher criminal legal system consequences.
- **Discrimination:** Many of these systems rely on historical data that reflect existing biases in policing and the criminal legal system. This leads to the over-policing of marginalized communities, particularly racialized groups, migrants, and low-income neighbourhoods. For instance, systems like VioGén and EPV-R use nationality and migration status as specific risk factors.
- **Transparency and accountability:** The use of these systems is often opaque, with little public awareness of their use. Freedom of Information Access requests are frequently denied, and there is no comprehensive public register of ADM systems in use. This lack of transparency prevents meaningful scrutiny and accountability.
- **Mass surveillance and the right to privacy:** 'Predictive' systems in policing and the criminal legal system rely on the collection and analysis of vast swathes of personal information by the state. Systems and databases in this report draw on sensitive information including nationality and ethnicity, gender, migration history, education and employment background, job position, facial images, and fingerprints. The level of data required to power predictive systems, and the highly personal information they draw on risks interfering with the right to a private life, free from unnecessary intrusion.

1 Introduction

In Spain, data-based and automated decision-making (ADM) systems are being used by police forces and criminal justice authorities, including prisons. These systems include so-called 'predictive' policing and crime 'prediction', profiling and 'risk' assessment systems and tools.

This report analyses some of the key systems and databases used in policing and criminal justice in Spain. It looks at how they work, how they influence real life decisions, and the impact they have. The analysis also explores how specific groups and communities are disproportionately targeted and impacted by these systems, including women, migrants, racialised minorities and non-nationals, people from working-class backgrounds or individuals affected by mental health issues.

Spain has several police forces. The National Police and Guardia Civil operate throughout the country, as do the Local Police and the municipal police forces, assigned to the different localities and provinces. In addition, the Mossos d'Esquadra and Ertzaintza operate in the autonomous communities of Catalonia and the Basque Country, respectively.

Each of these police forces are independent from each other. Although they collaborate through joint operations and sharing information, each force operates at different hierarchical levels and has different powers. For instance, while the National Police operates in urban areas, the Guardia Civil operates in rural areas. Therefore, each uses its own data, models and systems.

Given the media and political hype around artificial intelligence (AI), it is important to highlight that most of the data-based and algorithmic systems used by the police and criminal justice authorities in Spain do not use AI-based techniques. Similarly to systems used by police and criminal justice authorities elsewhere in Europe, they use more basic models that use classic statistical methods, such as risk assessment tools.

However, there are still significant issues with even these rule-based systems and tools. Some of them have been in use for more than ten years already, and yet they are used in a semi-secretive manner, with the public often not aware of their use. Many have never been assessed or audited by an independent body.

While the media, public discourse and legislators are focusing on the alleged risks that artificial general intelligence (AGI) may entail for society, low-profile automated systems and non-AI-powered tools used by police and criminal justice authorities already significantly and negatively impact people's lives. The consistent use of data-based and automated tools for making or influencing decisions and to evaluate people and suspects in criminal cases can cause discrimination. However, these systems have been in use for years and have not been subjected to any meaningful regulation, nor are there significant protections for people and their rights in relation to their use.

This calls into question whether these systems should be used at all. In June 2023, the

European Parliament voted to ban predictive policing and criminal prediction systems,⁸ and the EU's AI Act contains a (partial) ban on some of these systems.⁹

At the very least, it is crucial that there is scrutiny of these tools by civil society and other stakeholders who wish to understand the intricacies of such protocols. This report contributes to that scrutiny.

a) Methodology

This report has been produced by a cross-disciplinary team (one journalist and two academics) using a series of investigative techniques, following the guidance of the report's editors. The aim was to review existing information on the systems in this report and, in turn, to provide updated information on the systems, how they were developed, what data they use, who is using them and how. This information was then analysed to explore the possibility that these systems could be discriminating against certain populations. These methods were as follows:

- **Interviews.** As part of this research, we conducted interviews with academics and researchers, some of whom were directly or indirectly involved with the creation of the models, as well as others who were not directly involved but had an investigative background in the specific area that was being analysed.

Local and regional police departments were also interviewed, along with police officers and inspectors. These included the Mossos d'Esquadra in Catalonia and local police officials in cities such as Madrid or Valencia. City councils were also asked for interviews.

Organisations that have worked independently analysing or auditing some of the systems in question were also contacted, with the aim of understanding their impact on marginalised groups.

Interviews were also requested from the Ministry of Interior, including the managers and teams behind the systems and the academic collaborators who contributed to the creation of the models. However, these interviews were denied. This refusal to engage with our requests is discussed in detail below.

- **Freedom of Information Access (FOIA) requests.** Almost 20 requests were sent to different departments of the Spanish interior ministry, such as the National Police, the Guardia Civil or the Spanish Secretary General of Penitentiary Institutions, as well as local and regional branches, given that the Local Police and the Municipal Police operate at different levels to national law enforcement bodies.

⁸ Fair Trials, "EU Parliament approves landmark AI law", 16 June 2023. Available at: <https://www.fairtrials.org/articles/news/eu-parliament-approves-landmark-ai-law/>

⁹ European Commission (2024). 'AI Act', 7 March 2024: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/regulatory-framework-ai>

Transparency laws in Spain oblige ministerial departments to answer FOIA requests within one month. If the response to the request is favourable, with the request not being denied for security or commercial reasons, the response period can be extended by an additional month if the department considers the volume of requested information too complex or large.

- **Open source research.** We also conducted a search of public documentation that is not easily accessible with superficial information retrieval methods using search engines — commonly known as open source intelligence research (OSINT). Many of the briefings, statistics, evaluation reports and internal studies that are cited in this report have officially been made public by the Ministry of Interior and other authorities, but in practice are not always easily accessible by the public.

This report relies on information and data obtained from informative portals such as the Platform for Government Contracts — ‘Portal de Contratación del Sector Público’ in Spanish — where contract tenders and awards made to private companies by the public sector can be scrutinised; the registers of data processing activities which are mandatory under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR); and also the statistical portals of various bodies. These include the Crime Index reports of the Ministry of the Interior or the open data portal of the Mossos d'Esquadra, within the Generalitat de Catalunya.

- **Review of existing academic literature.** This is fundamental to understanding the landscape of data-based and ADM systems used in policing and criminal justice in Spain. Most of the systems in the report have been developed in-house by these authorities, rather than being outsourced to private companies. Most of the models developed in-house are done so in collaboration with academic researchers. In many cases, the authorities used data for these models collected from law enforcement bodies and other dependencies.

Virtually all the systems mentioned were created by collaboration between academic mathematicians and computer scientists, and the police or criminal justice authorities. In some cases, especially those systems which attempt to ‘predict’ human behaviour, psychologists, mediators and social workers also were involved in the process.

The results of these collaborations are sometimes reflected in scientific and/or academic studies describing the construction and/or performance of the model. In these cases, an in-depth review was conducted with the assistance of the collaborators of the report — both computer engineers with a background on the impact of ADM systems on marginalised communities — to extract relevant qualitative and quantitative data from the studies. For example, this included the accuracy percentage given to algorithms; the number of false positives or false negatives observed during testing phases; or the variables a model uses to extract conclusions.

- **Compilation of previous research.** This was based on investigations formerly carried out by the author and collaborators. Some of the algorithmic systems and computer software that appear in this report were researched in the past by the writers using similar techniques as the ones used for this report.

b) Obstruction and structural issues with transparency

It is clear from this report that the police and criminal justice authorities significantly limit the information put in the public domain. In 2023, we made multiple requests to interview representatives of different departments of the Ministry of Interior responsible for each system. Each of these requests was rejected after we explained the nature of the report. They were rejected even when the interviewees (usually academic researchers) agreed to respond to our questions individually.

Four months into the research, a member of the Ministry justified the denials to all requests for updated data and interviews under the pretext that the inquiries came from an "activist" organisation who conducted research into algorithmic discrimination and its impact.

Because the Ministry refused to engage and provide information, the relevant elements of this report are based on data that the Ministry has separately made public, as well as interviews with researchers working in the 'predictive' policing and crime 'prediction' and profiling sphere, and relevant academic literature, as specified in the 'Methodology' section above and compiled in the 'Bibliography' section at the end of this report.

Several FOIA requests were sent to different departments of the Ministry of Interior, but the information that was returned was sparse and evasive. In Spain, the Home Office has a long record of disregarding FOIA requests. In many cases, they ignore the deadlines set by the Spanish transparency law, resulting in administrative silence.¹⁰ After these cases are appealed before the Transparency Council and there is a favourable decision, a new time period is set for the corresponding department to deliver the requested information. However, the Ministry has simply ignored the outcomes of these appeals, and cases have to be taken to court to seek redress.¹¹

¹⁰ Europa Press. 15 de agosto 2022. 'Transparencia reprende al Gobierno por no argumentar su negativa a dar la información que le piden', <https://www.europapress.es/nacional/noticia-transparencia-reprende-gobierno-no-argumentar-negativa-dar-informacion-le-piden-20220815111551.html>

¹¹ Maldita.es. 16 de noviembre 2019. 'Interior recurre a los tribunales para evitar que se hagan públicos los informes de las muertes de migrantes en los CIE tras una petición de Maldita.es', <https://maldita.es/malditodato/20191116/interior-recurre-a-los-tribunales-para-evitar-que-se-hagan-publicos-los-informes-de-las-muertes-de-migrantes-en-los-cie-tras-una-peticion-de-maldita-es/>

2

'Predictive' policing: Location-focused crime 'prediction' systems

The use of automated decision-making and data-based predictive and profiling systems for location-focused crime 'prediction' has been identified in police departments across Europe: PAVED and Risk Terrain Modelling in France¹² Risk Terrain Modelling¹³ and other systems¹⁴ in the UK, KeyCrime's 'Delia'¹⁵ in Italy, or SKALA in Germany¹⁶ are just a handful of examples of algorithmic and data-based models being used to profile areas and identify supposed criminal 'hotspots'.¹⁷ Many of them are inspired by programmes used in the United States, where the 'predictive' policing tendencies started to proliferate.¹⁸

While location-focused 'predictive' systems proliferated first in the United States, systems used in Europe operate in a similar way. The systems use data about an area, including police and crime data, such as crimes or alleged crimes committed in an area, as well as other data such as stop and search or police check data, and sometimes non-police data like data on nationalities, socio-economic data, or other information about an area. The systems analyse this information and use it to make 'predictions' about where crime will be committed, or the 'risk' of crime occurring in a certain location or locations.

As these systems are developed and operated using 'crime' data, they inevitably focus on areas where there has been more recorded crime. This means that the neighbourhoods categorised as the most troubled are usually the ones most targeted by the police, which leads to a significantly closer scrutiny of their residents. This often includes racialised minorities, marginalised communities or areas with a lower socioeconomic status and fewer resources.

In Spain, location-focused 'predictive' policing systems and patrol optimization models are integrated into many police forces. There are several forces operating simultaneously: on the one hand, the National Police and the Guardia Civil operate throughout the country, while the Local Police and the municipal police forces are assigned to different localities and provinces.

In addition, the Mossos d'Esquadra and the Ertzaintza operate in the autonomous communities of Catalonia and the Basque Country respectively. Each police force is somewhat independent, which means that although they share operations and information, each works at different hierarchical levels. Therefore, each force also uses independent data, data-based systems and models.

¹² La Quadrature du Net (2023), "PREDICTIVE POLICING IN FRANCE: AGAINST OPACITY AND DISCRIMINATION, THE NEED FOR A BAN", <https://www.laquadrature.net/en/2024/01/18/predictive-policing-in-france-against-opacity-and-discrimination-the-need-for-a-ban/#:~:text=Predictive%20policing%20is%20thus%20still,as%20part%20of%20its%20prerogatives>

¹³ Metropolitan Police Service, 'MPS's use of the Risk Terrain Modelling Application', June 2023, <https://www.met.police.uk/foi-ai/metropolitan-police/disclosure-2023/june-2023/mps-use-risk-terrain-modelling-application/>

¹⁴ Liberty (2019), 'Policing by Machine', <https://www.libertyhumanrights.org.uk/issue/policing-by-machine/>

¹⁵ KeyCrime, "Delia", <https://keycrime.com/about-us>

¹⁶ North Rhine-Westphalia Police, @Project SKALA@, <https://polizei.nrw/artikel/projekt-skala-predictive-policing-in-nrw-ergebnisse>

¹⁷ Fair Trials. 'Automating Injustice: The use of Artificial Intelligence and automated decision-making systems in criminal justice in Europe', <https://www.fairtrials.org/articles/publications/automating-injustice>

¹⁸ ProPublica (2016), 'Machine Bias: There's software used across the country to predict future criminals. And it's biased against blacks', 23 May 2016, <https://www.propublica.org/article/machine-bias-risk-assessments-in-criminal-sentencing>; The Markup (2021), 'Crime Prediction Software Promised to Be Free of Biases. New Data Shows It Perpetuates Them', 2 Dec 2021, <https://themarkup.org/prediction-bias/2021/12/02/crime-prediction-software-promised-to-be-free-of-biases-new-data-shows-it-perpetuates-them>

a) 'Predictive Police Patrolling Decision Support System' (P3-DSS) or 'Smart Patrolling'

Use: Location-focused crime 'prediction'

Created: 2015

In 2015, the National Police tested a data-based 'predictive' model for 'smart patrolling'. It was developed by a former police inspector and mathematician, and two researchers in computer engineering and data science.¹⁹ The Predictive Police Patrolling Decision Support System (P3-DSS) aims to define time periods and locations where crimes could occur in the future.²⁰

DPPU: Data Pre-Processing Unit; CRFU: Crime Risk Forecasting Unit; PSOU: Patrol Sector Optimization Unit.
Contained in: "A Decision Support System for predictive police patrolling".

The first version of the system was trained on 105,755 reports of thefts from 2008 to 2012. It considered factors such as the isolation of certain areas (how far some districts are from each other), census data (because census districts have to match patrol allocations), the time of day and the number of patrols. The system assigned an optimal distribution of police resources to each of a city's neighbourhoods.

"The solution found by the algorithm is always better, an average improvement of 10%", stated one of the engineers working on the model, Dr Lara Quijano-Sánchez.²¹

The practical study divided the population into demographic groups residing in the Community of Madrid: Spaniards; other EU citizens; non-EU citizens; and groups for each continent. For each group the study then calculated their "police contact goal", i.e. the proportion of total police patrol time allocated to the group based on its size, in relation to the total population of the territory. Given the real-life configuration of police patrols, they calculated whether a population group was receiving more or less police attention than stated by the "police contact goal"

¹⁹ The same individuals created VeriPol, a predictive system analysing police reports, discussed in detail later in this report.

²⁰ Camacho-Collados, M., & Liberatore, F. (2015). A decision support system for predictive police patrolling. *Decision support systems*, 75, 25-37, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0167923615000834>

²¹ Quijano-Sánchez, L. (2022), 'Applications of AI and Data Science in Policing: 7 years of collaborations with the Spanish Police'. Lara Quijano-Sánchez, Ph.D by the Politechnic School of the Universidad Autónoma de Madrid. 25 January 2022, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=z8uBNNPtUmE>

The conclusion was that “there is a balance between efficiency in patrols and racial equity.” Reducing the efficiency of the algorithm from a 78% to a 75% would drastically improve the supposed ‘racial equity’ rate of the patrols.²² According to Quijano-Sánchez, the model would have to be tested in different areas with different population characteristics. For instance, in cities with “larger racial segregation”:

“A small reduction in efficiency leads to a huge increase in racial equality (...). Despite its activity, this model carries an ethical dilemma as it involves intentionally reducing the efficiency of patrol operations which may lead to more crime in the future”.²³

The researchers are now working on updates to the model which are intended to implement geographic, racial and workload fairness. “Even though the previous model defines efficient patrol configurations, it does not take into account racial equity and does not ensure that police presence is equitable among all different population groups,” Quijano-Sánchez explains.²⁴ The paper on the system published by Quijano-Sánchez and two colleagues in 2023 admits that “reported crimes are affected by selection biases driven by unequal crime reporting rates across socioeconomic groups and geographical areas”.²⁵

Over the last few years, research in the US has analysed the tendency of location-focused crime ‘prediction’ programs to single out neighbourhoods with high populations of racially minoritised people or people with lower incomes as more dangerous.²⁶ Further investigations (based on experiments done in Chicago) have also concluded that so-called predictive crime mapping “does not incur more precise applications of police force but rather legitimises the widespread criminalization of racialized districts”.²⁷ This means that police have relied on this kind of software for the supposed purpose of making their operations more objective, but in fact it has reinforced and exacerbated structural biases within policing, criminal justice and wider society.

The same issues are present in Spain. Anti-racist movements and fundamental rights organisations have repeatedly denounced racial profiling in police stops and identity checks, in which law enforcement and security forces motivate their actions on the basis of their appearance and not objective criteria. Police in Spain disproportionately stop and search people based on their racial, ethnic, or religious appearance, and this has been well documented by multiple studies.²⁸ For example, people from North and Central Africa and Eastern European countries are more likely to be subjected to identity checks than Spanish people.²⁹ This creates structural racial, socioeconomic and other biases in police data. Location-focused ‘predictive’ and ‘hotspot’ crime mapping systems are based on this data.

²² Ibid

²³ Ibid

²⁴ Ibid

²⁵ Liberatore, F., Camacho-Collados, M., & Quijano-Sánchez, L. (2023). Towards social fairness in smart policing: Leveraging territorial, racial, and workload fairness in the police districting problem. *Socio-Economic Planning Sciences*, 87, 101556, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0038012123000563#sec5>

²⁶ The Markup, (2021), ‘Crime Prediction Software Promised to Be Free of Biases. New Data Shows It Perpetuates Them’, December 2 2021, <https://themarkup.org/prediction-bias/2021/12/02/crime-prediction-software-promised-to-be-free-of-biases-new-data-shows-it-perpetuates-them>

²⁷ Jefferson, B. J. (2018). Predictable policing: Predictive crime mapping and geographies of policing and race. *Annals of the American Association of Geographers*, 108(1), 1-16, <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/24694452.2017.1293500>

²⁸ Rights International Spain y Open Society Justice Initiative (2019), “Under Suspicion: The Impact of Discriminatory Policing in Spain”, Report: <https://www.justiceinitiative.org/uploads/21ac6560-639d-461c-a6b7-06822ad1c07e/under-suspicion-the-impact-of-discriminatory-policing-in-spain-20190924.pdf>;

Video: <https://www.justiceinitiative.org/voices/under-suspicion-the-impact-of-discriminatory-policing-in-spain>

²⁹ Arenas-García L and García-España E, (2022), ‘Police stop and search in Spain: an overview of its use, impacts and challenges’, March 2022, <https://indret.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/1715.pdf>

b) EURO COP

Use: Location-focused 'crime prediction'

Date created: development began in 2014

EuroCop is a private company based in Madrid which produces and sells policing technology. Its product catalogue is wide-ranging: from common radars to so-called 'predictive' software that targets neighbourhoods according to their alleged criminality rates.

In the last two decades, EuroCop has signed more than 100 contracts with public administrations to supply them with location-focused crime 'prediction' technology.³⁰ It was bidding for a similar number of tenders in 2023 alone.

A diagram of the different systems provided by EuroCop. Credit: EuroCop ³¹

Spanish police started using EuroCop's products following a partnership with University Jaume I, based in Castellon, a Spanish city located in the Community of Valencia. In 2014, a group of academics started working on the development of mathematical models that would supposedly 'predict' increased rates of criminal activity. Those predictions were based on data generated by the police. The company financed the research that took place through a position the university called the "Eurocop Chair". This funding continued until 2020.

At the time this report was written, local police officers interviewed explained they used one of Eurocop's applications which was not based on artificial intelligence, but on statistical prediction models.

³⁰ El Salto. 'El Estado policial español 2.0: tecnologías de empresas privadas para vigilar a los ciudadanos'. 4 de febrero de 2021. <https://www.elsaltodiario.com/tecnologia/estado-policial-espanol-2.0-empresas-privadas--vigilar-ciudadanos>

³¹ EuroCop, 'Eurocop systems', <https://www.eurocop.com/sistemas-de-Eurocop/>

The EuroCop location-focused crime 'prediction' software had been employed or tested in seven regions:

- Alicante
- Andalucia
- the Canary Islands
- Castile and Leon
- the Community of Madrid;
- the Community of Valencia; and
- Galicia.³²

In the Community of Madrid, some police stations still use it. In the Community of Madrid, almost all police stations have now been using the platform for crime 'prediction' for nearly 10 years.

The EuroCop location-focused crime 'prediction' models use more-or-less the same training data to configure a map of 'hotspots' in a specific city. The programme draws on police data to map out areas where common crimes allegedly take place, such as violent or nonviolent theft, burglaries or vehicle thefts. It then uses statistical methods to establish a pattern and make a 'prediction' of where offences are likely to occur in future.

"Every three to six months there is an analysis done of the sectioning that the machine produces (...) and the allocation of resources of the Local Police is planned according to these inputs", says a former inspector of the Local Police of Rivas Vaciamadrid, a municipality to the east of Madrid and one of the first localities to work with EuroCop's predictive software.³³

Depending on the results of the system, the Local Police uses these 'predictions' to implement measures for surveillance, information-gathering, crime prevention and security control together with the Guardia Civil. For example, these can take the form of targeted police patrols to certain 'hotspot' streets or assigning vehicle units to specific neighbourhoods.

Data & criteria

According to the police officers interviewed, all data relating to a specific crime are fed into the EuroCop system. This is mainly obtained from complaints filed with the police. This data includes, amongst other things:

- the street where an alleged offence occurred;
- the time of day;
- the date;
- the number of people implicated;
- if there were any injuries;
- the crime type, etc.

One particular source of information is phone calls to emergency lines, amounting to some 20,000 inputs annually.

³² According to an interview with local police officers.

³³ Interview date 25th August 2023.

For example, to train newer models of such a system, a mathematician involved in the coordination of the “EuroCop Chair” at the time, used data from emergency calls received between 2011 and 2020 in the Community of Valencia. He said:

“You train it with a history of data and then validate it with the information of the latest year. Once you do that, you go to the future (where you can't test it because it doesn't exist yet); that is why you need the variables that are part of the history. How to predict the future? What you know, you know, and what you don't know you predict”.³⁴

The current Eurocop application used by local police also uses official crime statistics provided by the Ministry of Interior and statistical data from the Civil Guard. These are then combined with the police database for recorded crimes in each municipality. The aim was to connect these databases at a regional level, but this interoperability has not yet been achieved.

The database generated by the system contains “protected or highly protected personal data,” according to a former officer. Along with the name and ID of the victim of a crime, data related to health and social status is registered: “The people involved are identified along with all the information that may be useful to clarify what has happened or to inform welfare services, if necessary,” he said. For example, for a suicide attempt, any mental health conditions or other health and psychological data would be registered on the database, and social services would be involved.

The same police officer says that even though this data is registered, allegedly not all of it is used for this crime ‘prediction’: “We do not want to analyse the typology of the person committing the crime, but the type of crime and the area where it is committed”.

The areas identified by the programme are not public.

Impact

As noted in above-mentioned studies conducted in the US, the use of location-focused crime ‘prediction’ systems has reinforced systemic discrimination against racially minoritised and more deprived groups.

In the case of Rivas Vaciamadrid, a former inspector of the Local Police there points out that the neighbourhood most likely to be identified as a crime ‘hotspot’ by the EuroCop system is Cañada Real.³⁵ This is a low-income district in the outskirts of Rivas and the region of Madrid, where roughly 20,000 people live in very poor conditions, lacking even access to energy.³⁶

Related to this issue, the mathematician involved in the coordination of the “EuroCop Chair” believes that even if the discriminatory outputs from these programmes could supposedly be corrected within the data, there is still the fact that the systems appear to discriminate against certain neighbourhoods:

³⁴ Interview date 10th March 2023.

³⁵ Interview date 25th August 2023.

³⁶ elDiario.es. 31 de diciembre de 2022. ‘La Cañada Real, un barrio en (auto)construcción frente al estigma, el abandono y la presión inmobiliaria’: https://www.eldiario.es/sociedad/canada-real-barrio-auto-construccion-frente-estigma-abandono-presion-inmobiliaria_1_9830859.html

“A bias is produced when we say that a certain area is conflictive and more patrols are taken there. From a mathematical point of view, it can be corrected. From a social point of view, it is much more complicated to avoid being prejudiced because you live in certain areas that are considered to be more conflictive”.³⁷

Hundreds of localities continue to use EuroCop’s application, and EuroCop has implemented several updates to the system. The researchers who contributed to the creation of the models continue to adapt and improve them, but they don’t receive updated data from the police anymore. This means that the models continue to operate based on years-old historical data. The same mathematician claims that: “If you have a model that has been trained for eight years, what you do is you compare the model with real data from the last two years to validate it. If you find that there is an accuracy of 89%, it is enough. That is why we do not need new police data”.³⁸

The police have not evaluated the accuracy or effectiveness on their side either. According to the interviewed mathematician, the success of the algorithm is based on its theoretical feasibility; it can only be evaluated as successful by evaluating the prevention and deterrence of crime by the police.³⁹

Despite the lack of comprehensive data to assess the real performance of the algorithm, the new EuroCop models were to be sold in Central American countries such as Colombia, Mexico and Ecuador,⁴⁰ where conceptions of criminality, crime rates and causes vary exponentially from those in Spain. The University Jaume I research group who worked in the development of the model was offered a contract to build a model in Ecuador that could analyse data on a country-wide level: whether there had been a homicide; the type of weapon used; or in which areas different types of deaths could occur. With that aim, the Ministry of Interior provided data on homicide, murder, hired assassination and femicide.

c) DataWeb (Mossos d’Esquadra, Catalonia)

A similar location-focused crime ‘prediction’ program called DataWeb is used by the Mossos d’Esquadra in Catalonia. However, at the time this report was written, the software was in the process of being updated, so very little information could be obtained.

According to the Mossos d’Esquadra, the current model is older than EuroCop. It is fed with data extracted from crime reports. This includes names, addresses, telephone numbers, and affiliations, in addition to crime-related information, such as the place where the alleged incident, offence or arrest took place, and the time of day or the date.

Virtually all the data points used by the programme are available on the Mossos d’Esquadra open data portal.⁴¹ This contains data on multiple different types of offences, including murder and related offences, injury, public order, crimes against the constitution and more.

³⁷ Interview date 10th March 2023

³⁸ Interview date 10th March 2023

³⁹ Interview date 10th March 2023Ibid.

⁴⁰ According to the same interview held in March 2023.

⁴¹ Mossos D’Esquadra, ‘Crime data viewer’,

https://mossos.gencat.cat/ca/els_mossos_desquadra/indicadors_i_qualitat/dades_obertes/Visors_altres_dades/visor-de-dades/

Crime map delineating the localities of Catalonia according to the number and type of crimes and the dates on which they occurred. 42

42 Mossos D'Esquadra, 'Crime data viewer', https://mossos.gencat.cat/ca/els_mossos_desquadra/indicadors_i_qualitat/dades_obertes/Visors_altres_dades/visor-de-dades/

3

'Predictive' policing: Person-focused crime 'prediction', profiling and risk assessment systems

In Spain, data-based and automated decision-making (ADM) systems are used by law enforcement agencies for making 'predictions' about and profiling individuals. This is used primarily to assess 'risk' of violence or harm, but other systems have also been developed, such as for detecting false crime reports.

The systems consist primarily of statistical models that analyse variables about a person (such as age, gender, nationality, record of police contact) provided by the police or other agencies and, based on these, produce a specific output that is used to -support decision-making and alleged crime prevention. Outputs might be, for instance, the probability of a future event occurring, or a level of risk (of committing a criminal offence).

These variables are analysed against data about individuals which is entered into the system in question. This includes information gathered by the police: identifying information, socio-demographic data (such as age, gender or nationality), number of children, marital status, income, health condition, criminal record, family relationship, and more. These systems interpret and cross-reference all this information and produce an outcome.

This means that people targeted are subjected to a constant analysis of data that characterises them, their past and present lives and their relationships. The objective is to determine and 'predict' their behaviour, 'risk', or supposed 'criminality'. This has potential punitive and criminal justice consequences. Data-based and automated decision-making systems used by law enforcement agencies can influence and lead to outcomes that may include: increased monitoring or surveillance, stop and search, fines, questioning and arrests. They can also influence important decisions further into the criminal legal system, such as sentencing, parole, and prison categorisation.

This section analyses some of the better-known algorithmic and data-based systems used in Spain. They are mainly implemented by the police and are used to support decision-making, though their outputs are also sometimes used in judicial proceedings.

a) VioGén (National Police)

Use: Gender-based violence risk assessment system

Date created: 2007

Purpose & outcome

VioGén is one of the most well-known risk assessment systems in Spain. It is used by the National Police and owned by the Ministry of Interior. Its main purpose is to assess the risk of gender-based violence after an individual has reported an incident. It consists of a computer-based platform where the police manage information regarding gender-based violence cases, including reports of a case and a Police Risk Assessment (VPR hereinafter, its Spanish acronym).

The latest version of the VPR protocol (VPR 5.0), which was implemented in 2019, is made up of a 35-item questionnaire that quantifies different factors of risk: history of violence between a couple, characteristics of the offender, circumstances related to minors and other factors that are considered to aggravate the situation.⁴³

Officers mark each indicator depending on whether it is present (Yes) or not (No) when they collect the victim's testimony, but will also complement it with information they gather on the case. If the answer is not clear, some of the items include a "No answer / Don't know" option: for instance, when the victim does not know if the offender has a history of violence or does not know if they have shown controlling behaviours in recent months. The "No answer / Don't know" option also applies to questions that officers might not know beforehand, e.g. if the victim has children in their care.

After the completion of the questionnaire, a longer process begins. This involves the analysis of further data by officers to assign certain protection measures that match the level of risk provided. The risk score assigns one of the following categories: no risk, low, medium, high and extreme. A low score means that the police will check on the victim through phone calls, for example, while an extreme risk score may mean that the police will even monitor the victim's home or assign security patrols to ensure their safety.⁴⁴

The progress of the case is evaluated through another questionnaire, called "Evolution of the Police Risk Assessment" (VPER). According to its creators, "it operates fully autonomously, with its own algorithm, and is able to produce predictions using a mixed set of indicators (risk protection) to assess the likelihood of recidivism and at the same time monitor changes over time".⁴⁵

Figure 1: Schema of Viogen's working process.

Retrieved from: Quijano-Sánchez et al. (2021), "A twist in Intimate Partner Violence Risk Assessment Tools: Gauging the contribution of exogenous and historical variables", 25 December 2021, Vol: 234.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0950705121008480#preview-section-snippets>

⁴³ Area of Gender Violence, Studies and Training of the Ministry of Interior (2020), 'Guía de aplicación del formulario VFR5.0-H en la valoración forense del riesgo', <https://www.otrosi.net/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/GUIA-VALORACION-DEL-RIESGO-FORENSE.pdf>

⁴⁴ Secretary of State for Security, (2016) 'Instrucción nº 7/2016', 8 July 2016, https://violenciagenero.igualdad.gob.es/wp-content/uploads/Instruccion7_2016.pdf

⁴⁵ Ministry of Interior (2018), 'La valoración policial del riesgo de violencia contra la mujer pareja en España', September 2018, https://www.interior.gob.es/opencvms/pdf/archivos-y-documentacion/documentacion-y-publicaciones/publicaciones-descargables/seguridad-ciudadana/La_valoracion_policial_riesgo_violencia_contra_mujer_pareja_126180887.pdf

The VPER assessment algorithm is made up of 43 items divided into categories similar to those in VPR — mostly the ones related to alleged criminality. In addition, it incorporates a question on the victim's own perception of their risk. The VPER model is activated to monitor increases and decreases in risk, and will remain active depending on the level that is ascribed. This means that the risk assessment algorithm will be re-applied within 72 hours if the risk is extreme; within 7 days if it's high; every 30 days when the risk is medium; and every 60 days when it's low.

Police officers can modify the result of the algorithm's assessment, but only to increase the level of risk. The most cited study in evaluations of the algorithm's performance is a 2014 PhD thesis which concluded that in 95% of cases, police officers maintain the VioGén algorithm's risk score and allocate protection measures accordingly.⁴⁶ Thus, the vast majority of decisions are essentially automated, rather than made by people. Meaningful human involvement is necessary in this process, especially when inputting questionnaire answers after listening to the victim's testimony, and supervising the outputs of risk levels.

By September 2023, the VioGén system had assessed around 770,000 cases.⁴⁷ As pointed out by Eticas Foundation, over the years, the risk scores assigned by the algorithm have been quite stable. The most frequently assigned levels by far are "no risk" and "low". This is inversely proportional to the number of active cases, which is growing every year: "While the distribution of risk categories has been stable over time, every year there are more cases with higher risk scores that require special police attention".⁴⁸

Data & criteria

VioGén draws on data from alleged offender's criminal records and any prisoner records, such as granting of permits or release from prison. This information also includes sentencing measures other than imprisonment, such as being subjected to restraining orders, fines, probation or community service orders. VioGén also registers identifying data such as identity card or driving licence number, photographs, phone numbers, addresses, email and vehicle ownership.

When it comes to characteristics of the victims and the aggressors, VioGén includes data regarding gender, nationality, working status, health information, occupation, education level and marital status.⁴⁹ From this, the VPR questionnaire considers risk factors such as whether: the victim is a non-national; the aggressor is under 24; or there are circumstances related to mental health. These include, for example, if the offender has a "mental and/or psychiatric disorder" or whether they show signs of attempted suicide.

The algorithm is actuarial. This means that all the items assessed by the algorithm sum up to the final result, but the algorithm's creators may grant some of them a larger predictive value.

⁴⁶ Bayona, J. Z. (2014). *Violencia contra la mujer: marco histórico evolutivo y predicción del nivel de riesgo* (Tesis doctoral, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid), <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/servlet/tesis?codigo=43479>

⁴⁷ Ministry of Interior. 'Statistical data VioGen'. September 2023. <https://www.interior.gob.es/opencms/pdf/servicios-al-ciudadano/violencia-contra-la-mujer/estadisticas/2023/Estadistica-Septiembre-2023.pdf>

⁴⁸ Eticas Research (2022), 'The external audit of the VioGen system', 8 March 2022, <https://eticasfoundation.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/ETICAS-FND-The-External-Audit-of-the-VioGen-System.pdf>

⁴⁹ Ministry of Interior. 'Registro de actividad de tratamientos del Ministerio del Interior'. Updated March 2025., <https://transparencia.gob.es/transparencia/dam/jcr:b3eb17bc-b1a7-4092-9c99-f11f62d868ae/20241211%20Inventario%20de%20Actividades%20de%20Tratamiento%20del%20Ministerio%20del%20Interior.pdf>

A 2017 study on the penultimate version explains that the following 13 indicators have been programmed with extra weight: ⁵⁰

1. Serious or very serious physical violence;
2. Serious or very serious sexual violence;
3. Use of weapons (not guns);
4. Death threats from the offender;
5. Upscale of the aggressions or threats in the last six months;
6. Signs of extreme jealousy from the offender in the last six months;
7. Signs of harassment from the offender in the last six months;
8. The offender has attacked other people or animals in the last year;
9. The offender has a mental disorder;
10. The offender shows signs of suicide attempts;
11. The offender has an addiction to or abuses alcohol, drugs or medicines;
12. The victim has expressed their intent to end the relationship in the last six months;
13. The victim thinks the offender is capable of attacking them or killing them.

As of April 2022, the team managing and monitoring the programme consisted of 22 people, but there are around 40,000 public servants with access to the system.⁵¹ This implies that not everyone who interacts with it has the same level of training on gender-based violence, or on operating the system and interpreting its results. This could lead to possible misclassifications of the risk level a survivor being assessed actually faces.

Impact

A significant barrier to understanding the full impact of VioGén is that the Ministry of Interior has never released enough data to independent bodies for them to conduct a full external audit. Reviews of the system and the algorithm have always been carried out by people involved in its development, or by the staff of the Ministry department who oversee and manage it.

The Ministry of Interior had commissioned a report on VioGén's performance from researchers at the University of Valencia, who will then hand over their report to Amnesty International for an assessment of the strengths and weaknesses of the system.⁵² As of October 2023, Amnesty International said they had not received further information on the matter. Even if this process were to be completed as outlined, it would still not constitute a full and meaningful algorithmic audit of the system.

Éticas Research, along with others in Spain, have been requesting access to the source code of the system since 2018. Numerous FOIA requests about the system have been denied in recent years on the grounds that the information cannot be released due to security concerns.

⁵⁰ López-Ossorio, J. J., Álvarez, J. L. G., Pascual, S. B., García, L. F., & Buela-Casal, G. (2017), 'Risk factors related to intimate partner violence police recidivism in Spain', *International Journal of Clinical and Health Psychology*, 17(2), 107-119, <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/metricas/documentos/ARTREV/6001491>

⁵¹ La Moncloa. 'El Sistema VioGén supera los seis millones de valoraciones de riesgo a víctimas de violencia de género'. 19 de mayo de 2023. <https://www.lamoncloa.gob.es/serviciosdeprensa/notasprensa/interior/Paginas/2023/190523-sistema-viogen-victimas-violencia-genero.aspx>

⁵² El País (2022), 'VioGén: visita a las tripas del algoritmo que calcula el riesgo de que una mujer sufra violencia machista', 10 April 2022, <https://elpais.com/tecnologia/2022-04-10/viogen-visita-a-las-tripas-del-algoritmo-que-calcula-el-riesgo-de-que-una-mujer-sufra-violencia-machista.html>

In spite of this, Eticas Foundation conducted an independent audit of the system in 2022 along with the Ana Bella Foundation, a support network and programme for survivors of gender-based violence in Spain. The audit consisted of: analysis of 126 homicides documented by the General Council of the Judiciary where the victim had previously reported their aggressor for gender-based violence; interviews with 31 women who had been assessed by VioGén; enquiries to seven lawyers specialising in gender-based violence; and a performance analysis of the algorithm based on public data from the Ministry of Interior.⁵³

The audit found that the system did not process the testimonies of the victims who reported cases of gender-based violence. Instead, it used the adapted version that police officers create when they interrogate them. This means that the indicators present in the VioGén evaluation depend on the decisions of the police officer undertaking the assessment, which will change the victim's resulting risk score. The questions also seem to be too rigid: sometimes people are obliged to answer strictly with a 'yes' or a 'no', or find themselves under great pressure to answer appropriately.⁵⁴

Furthermore, VioGén risk scores are calculated based on information about victims of gender-based violence who have reported their cases. However, many experiences of gender-based violence go unreported, particularly those of women from marginalised and more deprived backgrounds.

The study by Eticas Foundation and Ana Bella Foundation delved into the specific characteristics of the women analysed in the sample group and identified certain barriers that stopped them from reporting an assault and subsequently being evaluated by VioGén. This included their socio-economic status and their emotional processing of their experiences of gender-based violence. Migrant women, women from more deprived backgrounds, and women with children are the most affected by structural difficulties in reporting their aggressors, as well as LGBTQIA+ people and people with disabilities. It was noted that migrant women in particular may not report due to "being in an irregular status for their stay in Spain and fearing deportation."⁵⁵ This raises concerns that VioGén may not fully account for the experiences of those most marginalised in society.⁵⁶

"Three of the cases in our fieldwork showed how the same gender-violence case received different treatment by different police officers. W13, who is a gender-violence victim of migrant-origin, had to travel to another city to be able to report the aggression by her partner. Only after doing so, she could be evaluated by the VioGén system, and she received a high-risk score".⁵⁷

"As W3 explained to us that her irregular status blocked her from seeking help. Her aggressor constantly told her that she cannot do anything, because otherwise she gets deported. She said: 'I didn't get in touch with any organizations, I didn't have any support and I was completely alone'".⁵⁸

53 Eticas Research (2022), 'The external audit of the VioGen system', 8 March 2022. <https://eticasfoundation.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/ETICAS-Auditoria-Externa-del-sistema-VioGen--20220308.docx-2.pdf>

54 Ibid

55 Ibid

56 Ibid

57 Ibid

58 Ibid

Out of the 31 women interviewed, 15 rated their experience with VioGén negatively; 10 reported both negative and positive aspects; and six rated their overall experience positively. According to Eticas, out of the 126 cases that were included in the sample, 55 had received an inaccurate risk score, representing 43% of the sample group. This means that the assessed risk was low or unperceived and the necessary protection measures were not adopted: ⁵⁹

“As with any data system, the quality of the inputted data is key to the quality, representativity and fairness of its results. The factors identified translate into poor or biased inputs in 80% of the cases. While we may not generalise from our small sample, the results obtained point to the urgent need to revise the conditions in which women access the system and the questionnaire”. ⁶⁰

VioGén has significant consequences for victims from the moment they report an experience of gender-based violence. As explained above, the protection measures assigned to each victim depend on the level of risk assigned: a low score may mean that police will check on the victim frequently through phone calls, while an extreme risk score may subject a victim to continuous monitoring, increased surveillance in the form of security patrols or home checks. For victims from communities who are already disproportionately targeted by police, such as women from racially minoritised or more deprived backgrounds, this may increase the likelihood of criminal justice outcomes for them or those around them.

VioGén is held in high-esteem internationally for being one of the first systems of its kind to conduct gender-based violence risk assessments. However, the evidence arising from these independent studies raise questions as to whether ADM systems are the best method for assessing the cases of women who have experienced gender-based violence.

The press department of the Ministry of Interior refused requested interviews with the main psychologist behind the development and current use of VioGén, Dr Juan José López Ossorio. López Ossorio is Head of the Analysis VioGén and Criminality Area at the Security Secretariat at the Ministry of Interior. Although he was in favour of collaborating with the research for this report, this was blocked by the communications department.

b) EPV-R (Ertzaintza, Basque Country & judiciary, Basque Country)

Used for: Gender-based violence risk assessment

Created: 2005

Purpose & outcome

Since 2007, the local police force of the northern region of Spain of the Basque Country — the Ertzaintza — has been using EPV-R, an in-house tool to assess the risk that gender-based violence victims will be assaulted again by their aggressors. The system differs from VioGén in the data that it uses; the questions that are asked of victims; and the dynamics of the computer programme on which it runs. The final goal however is similar: to assign different levels of protection to women who report cases of gender-based violence.

⁵⁹ Ibid

⁶⁰ Ibid

EPV-R stands for Intimate Partner Femicide and Severe Violence Assessment (“Escala de predicción del riesgo de violencia grave contra la pareja” in Spanish). The second part of the model’s name was added in 2010, which signals that the model was revised (“revisado”). It was revised again, in 2012. Since 2013 the system has not been modified further.

EPV-R consists of a questionnaire with 20 questions. The answers are combined to provide a maximum score of 48 points. If this score exceeds 24 points, the risk ascribed to the victim is severe; over 18 points is high; more than 10 is medium; and below nine, low. Depending on the resulting level of risk, the Ertzaintza applies different protection measures for the victim which can include: interviews; arbitrary home visits and phone calls; individual transport to courts; 24/7 monitoring; and the assignment of escort patrols.

The system includes the questionnaire and runs on a digital platform called EBA (Emakumeen eta Etxekoen Babesa in Euskera, the language of the Basque Country – which means Protection of Women and Households).⁶¹ This is the software that the Ertzaintza uses to register all information on gender-based violence cases, including the score provided by EPV-R. It operates in a similar way to VioGén.

EPV-R is first used in the initial stage of investigations. The police officers ask the victims a set of questions and assign each answer a value between zero and three points. Not all questions are assigned the same predictive value and they are not asked in a fixed order. Generally, those related to the offender’s use of violence or a violent history of the offender are classified as a major risk:

ESCALA DE PREDICIÓN DE RIESGO DE VIOLENCIA GRAVE CONTRA LA PAREJA (EPV-R)
En la ERTZAINZA desde el 25-05-2013

Nombre: _____ Expediente: _____
Fecha: _____ Evaluador: _____

I. Datos personales		Valoración
1.	Procedencia extranjera del agresor o de la víctima	0 o 1
II. Situación de la relación de pareja en los 6 últimos meses		Valoración
2.	Separación reciente o en trámites de separación	0 o 1
3.	Acoso reciente a la víctima o quebrantamiento de la orden de alejamiento	0 o 2
III. Tipo de violencia en los 6 últimos meses		Valoración
4.	Existencia de violencia física susceptible de causar lesiones	0 o 2
5.	Violencia física en presencia de los hijos u otros familiares	0 o 2
6.	Aumento de la frecuencia y de la gravedad de los incidentes violentos	0 o 3
7.	Amenazas graves o de muerte	0 o 3
8.	Amenazas con objetos peligrosos o con armas de cualquier tipo	0 o 3
9.	Intención clara de causar lesiones graves o muy graves	0 o 3
10.	Agresiones sexuales en la relación de pareja	0 o 2
IV. Perfil del agresor		Valoración
11.	Celos muy intensos o conductas controladoras sobre la pareja en los 6 últimos meses	0 o 3
12.	Historial de conductas violentas con una pareja anterior	0 o 2
13.	Historial de conductas violentas con otras personas (amigos, compañeros de trabajo, etc.)	0 o 3
14.	Consumo actual abusivo de alcohol y/o drogas	0 o 3
15.	Abandono de tratamientos psiquiátricos o psicológicos en el caso de existir una enfermedad mental	0 o 1
16.	Conductas habituales de crueldad, de desprecio a la víctima y/o de falta de arrepentimiento	0 o 3
17.	Justificación de las conductas violentas.	0 o 3
V. Vulnerabilidad de la víctima		Valoración
18.	Percepción de la víctima de peligro de muerte en el último mes	0 o 3
19.	Intentos de retirar denuncias previas o de echarse atrás en la decisión de abandonar o denunciar al agresor	0 o 3
20.	Vulnerabilidad de la víctima por razón de enfermedad, soledad o dependencia	0 o 2

VALORACIÓN DEL RIESGO DE VIOLENCIA GRAVE			
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Básico (0-9)	Moderado (10-17)	Alto (18-23)	Especial (24-48)

EPV-R questionnaire used by the Ertzaintza. Credit: AlgorithmWatch (2023), ‘Basque Country: how an algorithm to assess the risk of gender-based violence sees people from “different cultures”’, 30 March 2023, <https://algorithmwatch.org/en/basque-country-gender-violence-algorithm/>

⁶¹ Ertzaintza. ‘Gender violence’, <https://www.ertzaintza.euskadi.eus/lfr/web/ertzaintza/violencia-de-genero>

A chief inspector of the Ertzaintza who was involved in the development of EBA has said the risk assessment score provided by EPV-R can be increased, but not reduced:

“Every time we receive new information we make a new risk assessment; the score can coincide with the previous one or not. Normally, it increases. We then add that score to the evaluation that is done by the Operation Headquarters at the victim’s house and the one carried out at the police station after the complaint. We then count with at least four risk assessments in the first few hours of a case”.⁶²

The fact that the score cannot be decreased is a form of bias within the system, as it means that the system is structured to only increase an individual’s risk score, and therefore is more likely to produce a high-risk score for an individual.

Using these evaluations and the rest of the information from the victim’s and the offender’s profiles in EBA — which includes personal and health data, relationship status, and the reports of the officials — the Ertzaintza then assign different measures of protection to the victim.

Unlike other ADM systems used in policing, the score provided by EPV-R is also included in reports received by judges on gender-based violence court cases in the Basque Country. The reports they receive include the following notification that EPV-R was used to generate a risk score:

“The purpose of making an assessment of the level of risk the victim faces is to articulate the appropriate personal protection measures to each case and each moment, with the aim to prevent new aggressions and protect her appropriately”.⁶³

Over the years, the Ertzaintza has started to use the tool to try to detect possible cases of vicarious violence, as well as signs of suicide attempts by the offender. This is done by analysing the parameters related to violence and the presence of children in the case, along with other personal and health data of the people involved. This information is also included in the reports provided to judges.

A former examining judge in the Basque Country who worked on gender-based violence cases, confirmed that he would receive a document with a risk assessment grade in each report. He explained that in 2023 police began including a more detailed explanation about the scoring system, including a list of the 20 items EPV-R evaluates. Next to each item, they added an ‘S’ (Yes) or an ‘N’ (No), depending on whether the variable was present in the case.⁶⁴ The EPV-R system can therefore influence judicial decision-making.

Data & criteria

EPV-R is only one of the elements that are integrated into the EBA platform, where all case-related information is managed. Specifically, the Ertzaintza collect information about the victims or “people affected by situations of domestic and/or gender-based violence”, as well

⁶² Interview date 14th February 2023.

⁶³ According to internal documentation provided by a judge who operated in the Basque Country.

⁶⁴ Ertzaintza, ‘EBA. Data controller’, <https://www.ertzaintza.euskadi.eus/lfr/documents/62347/4519349/4.+EBA.pdf/6a372e0e-66a4-bde6-1c6f-1abca3acb950?t=1639567729630>

as suspected offenders and people who have been convicted. It also includes information about Ertzaintza members and police officers involved in the case.⁶⁵

The Ertzaintza store the following information about people:

- identification data;
- photographs;
- personal characteristics data;
- health data “when necessary, due to the nature of the case”;
- data relating to the commission of criminal offences;
- measures taken; and
- information on the management of police actions, including the possession of weapons.

This is stored in EBA, along with the information channelled by EPV-R at the moment of interviewing the victim.

EPV-R, like many other automated risk assessment tools, has been developed with the supervision of psychologists. Its creators collaborated closely with the Ertzaintza to establish and later refine the parameters that should be analysed. According to their research, the average age of alleged gender-based violence perpetrators is 37 years, while the average victims are two years younger. This same research claims that the migration rate among the alleged offenders is 30%, which means that approximately one in every three alleged offenders are non-nationals.⁶⁶ This assessment is likely to be skewed based on the rate that people from different ethnicities and backgrounds are reported to the police. The system’s creators also point to data which states that 28% of victims are not Spanish nationals, but Latin American, African (mostly Moroccan) and Eastern European (mostly Romanian) women.

Impact

The Ertzaintza stated in 2023 that, since 2011, when it started using the revised version of the tool, no victims under their protection have been murdered. This relates to the whole protocol, including the management that takes place through EBA, not just the application of EPV-R.

Regarding the performance of the questionnaire, a preliminary study was conducted in 2022 by researchers Ana Valdivia and Cari Hyde-Vaamonde, along with the judge Julian García. Their conclusions are that half of the time (53%), the system would assign a low risk to cases that had actually been catalogued as high risk.⁶⁷

According to García, the data used in EPV-R can cause issues due to the subjective way in which it is analysed: “The questions in the tool place a high value on the use of weapons or signs of physical violence, therefore the result was not as reliable in cases where this circumstance was not documented,” he recalls.⁶⁸ He outlined an example of a woman who

⁶⁵ Ertzaintza, ‘EBA. Data controller’, <https://www.ertzaintza.euskadi.eus/lfr/documents/62347/4519349/4.+EBA.pdf/6a372e0e-66a4-bde6-1c6f-1abca3acb950?t=1639567729630>

⁶⁶ Echeburúa, E., Amor, P. J., Loinaz, I., & De Corral, P. (2010). Escala de Predicción del Riesgo de Violencia Grave contra la pareja-Revisada-(EPV-R). *Psicothema*, 22(4), 1054-1060, <https://www.psicothema.com/pdf/3840.pdf>

⁶⁷ Valdivia, A., Hyde-Vaamonde, C., & García-Marcos, J. (2022). Judging the algorithm: A case study on the risk assessment tool for gender-based violence implemented in the Basque country. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2203.03723*, <https://arxiv.org/abs/2203.03723>

⁶⁸ AlgorithmWatch (2023). ‘Basque Country: how an algorithm to assess the risk of gender-based violence sees people from “different cultures”’. 30 March 2023, <https://algorithmwatch.org/en/basque-country-gender-violence-algorithm/>

was being stalked by her partner. The man would sit in front of her house and at night disturb her child, who developed mental health issues. García decided to grant a protection order and classified the risk as high, but EPV-R had given that particular case a low score.⁶⁹

This argument is also upheld by Ana Valdivia, who is a researcher at the Oxford Internet Institute and member of AlgoRace, and also a collaborator of this report: “The problem lies in quantifying measures that are too subjective”. For example, when examining cruelty or jealousy patterns:

“The number of false negatives is higher than true positives when the cutoff score is 10. This means that the assessment tool is more likely to classify severe cases as non-severe at this score, which could imply the underestimation of cases”.

Each of the questions and data points is open to subjective analysis and they cannot always be answered with a categorical answer. This means that the data can be influenced by individual, institutional and structural biases.

As a clear example, the system uses data that discriminates against migrants and people of certain nationalities. For example, one question asks about the origin of the offender and the victim: “Offender or victim is an immigrant”. The inclusion of such data is discriminatory. An affirmative answer to this question could increase the ‘risk’ score- and is likely to influence discriminatory outcomes against migrants.

Oskar Fernandez from the Ertzaintza explained that this item doesn’t apply to all non-nationals, but those “who have a culture other than the Western one.”⁷⁰ The example he gave then is that a person from France or the French Basque Country wouldn’t count as a non-national in most cases, and that it is up to the officers interviewing each victim to assess this. “It [the item on nationality] would only apply where there exists a different cultural understanding than the European when it comes to a couple”.⁷¹

There is no methodology for officers to follow in relation to how to include the nationality variable in the overall risk assessment, or a specific list of countries that are considered riskier than others and that officers can consult. This means that the decision on whether to assign more points of risk by labelling someone as ‘immigrant’ or not is subjective, and will largely depend on the officer’s cultural assumptions and unconscious bias.

There is no clear definition as to what a “European couple” stands for: would a Romanian person be labelled as riskier than a British one? This freedom of interpretation invalidates the implication that using an algorithmic or automated programme to deliberate on gender-based violence cases (or other types of assessments) make the process more objective. The inclusion of this variable increases the potential for discrimination against people from racialised and Global Majority backgrounds.

⁶⁹ Ibid

⁷⁰ Ibid

⁷¹ Ibid

c) Sexual aggressors profiling (National Police)

Used for: Prediction of sexual aggressors' identity

Date created: In development

The Spanish Civil Guard are currently working on a statistical tool that will attempt to profile and 'predict' potential suspects of sexual assaults, as well as the area in which they may be found. The aim is to have preliminary data before starting an investigation, to help psychologists and criminologists narrow down the search for possible aggressors in cases where they have not been identified by the victim.⁷²

The Judicial Police section of the Civil Guard, in collaboration with a researcher from Complutense University, has created and defined five profiles for alleged aggressors and five predominant types of assault. These are based on historical police data:

1. Non-nationals under 25 or between 32 and 20 years old, with no criminal history or administrative offences, who reside more than a kilometre from the scene of the crime.
2. Non-nationals with traffic offences who live less than one kilometre away from the scene of the crime (no specific age).
3. Spaniards under 25 who live less than one kilometre away from the victim, with a police record (for non-violent and non-sexual offences), but with administrative offences.
4. Spaniards between 32 and 40 years old with a history of non-sexual violence and administrative infractions who live far from the place where the assault took place.
5. Men under 25 or over 40 with a history of sexual offences who live close to the scene of the crime, without addiction problems.⁷³

The automated tool is supposed to cross-check these profiles (along with others on the type of crime) with the information provided by the victim, and produce an estimate of the area in which the offender might be located and their potential profile.

Academics who have collaborated previously with the Ministry of Interior state that building an efficient prediction tool for identifying sexual aggressors would require many more data points than those included in police statements. Previous studies on gender-based violence have used data on how the aggression took place, but the academics state that for profile-building and identification, personal and psychological variables must also be taken into account: age, nationality, mental health issues, disabilities, filiation data, and criminal record, amongst others.

The Ministry of the Interior refused to release further information on the tool on the grounds that the development of the system is at a preliminary stage, and therefore information on it is not of public interest. They only confirmed that the tool used logistic regression, a supervised form of machine learning, and that at the time of writing this report it had not been "used" or "tested" by State Security Forces other than the Civil Guard.⁷⁴

⁷² El País (2023), 'Inteligencia artificial para atrapar a los violadores', 28 February 2023, <https://elpais.com/sociedad/2023-02-28/inteligencia-artificial-para-atrapar-a-los-violadores.html>

⁷³ Ibid

⁷⁴ According to interviews conducted on the matter for the elaboration of the report, 1st September 2023.

d) VeriPol (National Police)

Use: Identification of false crime reports

Created in: 2017

Purpose & outcome

VeriPol is an algorithmic system used by the National Police to detect false crime reports. The system is a 'natural language processing system', which scans the texts of reports on robbery, pickpocketing and purse snatching. It is effectively used as a lie detector; it was created to prevent fraud resulting from false reports and its main aim is to provide officers with a quick evaluation on whether a crime report is potentially false or not.

VeriPol is an unprecedented algorithmic system and has been referenced internationally as such.⁷⁵ The Spanish National Police started using it in 2018 and, as of 2023, is the only security force with access to it. The system was also meant to be deployed for the Guardia Civil, but this has not yet happened.

The programme was created by the team responsible for other police systems used in Spain, including VioGén and 'smart patrolling' algorithmic systems – a mathematician who is a former police officer, and two computer scientists who mostly work in the 'predictive' policing sphere.

VeriPol is used as follows: a person reports a crime related to robbery, pickpocketing or purse snatching to the police. The officer who interviews the alleged victim takes detailed notes and passes the resulting text through VeriPol. The software then assesses the likelihood that the claim is true or false, and gives police officers guidance on what path to follow if they were to investigate a possible crime. No information or statistics are available on how often the police do or do not follow the algorithm's indications.

A complaint is only considered 'false' once the complainant has admitted that they have lied to the police. This means, theoretically, that the mere application of the algorithm does not determine that a person is accused of a false complaint.

The algorithm was first tested in 2017 in Murcia and Málaga,⁷⁶ two Spanish cities located in south eastern and southern Spain respectively. According to its creators, the pilot project resulted in an increase in the number of false allegation cases that were resolved: 839.4% in the case of Murcia and 303.6% in Málaga. The study that resulted from the pilot project concluded that the system correctly detected false claims 90% of the time.⁷⁷

⁷⁵ Nature 'Police use a computer to expose false testimony'. 30 May 2018, <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-018-05285-9>

⁷⁶ Quijano-Sánchez, L (2022), 'Applications of AI and Data Science in Policing: 7 years of collaborations with the Spanish Police', Lara Quijano-Sánchez, Ph.D by the Politechnic School of the Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, 25 January 2022, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=z8uBNNPtUmE>

⁷⁷ Quijano-Sánchez, L., Liberatore, F., Camacho-Collados, J., & Camacho-Collados, M. (2018), 'Applying automatic text-based detection of deceptive language to police reports: Extracting behavioral patterns from a multi-step classification model to understand how we lie to the police'. Knowledge-Based Systems, 149, 155-168, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S095070511830128X?via%3Dihub>

According to data provided by the Ministry of Interior in 2020, VeriPol classifies around one in 20 reports as 'simulations of crime', meaning the claim is false ('simulation of crime' is itself a crime in Spain).⁷⁸ VeriPol is installed in around 240 police stations, almost all of them in the country.

Data & criteria

VeriPol was trained on 1,122 reports submitted to the police in 2015. They were all reviewed by one officer over the following two years, who catalogued 588 of them as false and 534 as real. Of course, not all of those cases had been resolved, which means that the model was built using assumptions made by the police officer who reviewed them, as "the real ratio of false reports" was unknown.⁷⁹

The initial model underpinning VeriPol was also trained on data from testimonies submitted to hotels, restaurants or health clinics. These included fake reviews or complaints about scams.⁸⁰

To validate the model, the scientists gave two new officers a subsample of 659 reports. They concluded that while both officers performed similarly, VeriPol "significantly outperforms the human experts (...) obtaining an improvement of more than 15% versus Evaluator 1 and more than 20% versus Evaluator 2".⁸¹

VeriPol's creators suggest that the algorithm has a tendency to err towards classifying true reports as false. The ratio of false positives for VeriPol is 9.54%, which means that for every ten complaints analysed by the system, one is wrongly classified as false.

'Applications of AI and Data Science in Policing: 7 years of collaborations with the Spanish Police'.
By Lara Quijano-Sánchez, Ph.D by the Politechnic School of the Universidad Autónoma de Madrid.

⁷⁸ AlgorithmWatch (2020), 'Spanish police plan to extend use of its lie-detector while efficacy is unclear', 27 October 2020, <https://algorithmwatch.org/en/spain-police-veripol/>

⁷⁹ Quijano-Sánchez, L., Liberatore, F., Camacho-Collados, J., & Camacho-Collados, M. (2018), 'Applying automatic text-based detection of deceptive language to police reports: Extracting behavioral patterns from a multi-step classification model to understand how we lie to the police', Knowledge-Based Systems, 149, 155-168, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S095070511830128X?via%3DIhub>

⁸⁰ Quijano-Sánchez, L. (2022), 'Applications of AI and Data Science in Policing: 7 years of collaborations with the Spanish Police' Lara Quijano-Sánchez, Ph.D by the Politechnic School of the Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, 25 January 2022, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=z8uBNNPtUmE>

⁸¹ Ibid

Technically, VeriPol does not process personal data because it only analyses the text of the report, submitted by the officer who drafted it. The model was also constructed by anonymizing the set of reports analysed and verified by the police, in order to prevent unconscious bias in the results.

Several words have been categorised by VeriPol as belonging to “true” or “false” reports. For instance, the appearance of the words: “to pull out,” “shove,” “insurance”, “back” (as in the body part), “lawyer”, “day”, “hand bag”, “felony”, “two hundred”, “helmet”, “mobile phones”, “shoulder” or the reference to “black” clothes, would indicate that the report is false. On the other hand, mentioning the words “bus”, “to kill”, “pendant”, “taken”, “stolen”, “plate” (as in registration plate), “officer”, “neck”, “chain”, “entrance hall”, would probably lead the algorithm into assessing the report as true.

Regarding the ways that complainants have described people, the words “face”, “beard”, “hair”, “brunette/dark-skinned”, “thin”, “age”, “Chinese” or “male” will likely make the algorithm classify a report as true.

Impact

Multiple studies have shown how natural language processing systems reproduce the biases that are inherent in society and represented in the language we use.⁸² For example, one study of a Google News text-based AI system found that ‘whites’ was associated with ‘parliamentarian’, ‘advocate’, ‘legislator’ and ‘lawyer’, while ‘minorities’ was associated with ‘butler’ and ‘footballer’.⁸³ Other studies have shown how these systems are not able to appreciate linguistic variation among different ethnic groups, misunderstanding and misclassifying the language and meanings.

Some critics of VeriPol consider that the diversity of the Spanish language cannot be sufficiently represented in the model, as multiple dialects are spoken with different words and expressions that are characteristic of each region and sub-region. Not only that, but the migrant population residing in the country, who may or may not be more fluent in the language, would not be well-represented either. Furthermore, women might be less likely to describe a situation of conflict in front of a policeman.⁸⁴

Some critics of VeriPol consider that the diversity of the Spanish language cannot be sufficiently represented in the model, as multiple dialects are spoken with different words and expressions that are characteristic of each region and sub-region. Not only that, but the migrant population residing in the country, who may or may not be more fluent in the language, would not be well-represented either. Furthermore, women might be less likely to describe a situation of conflict in front of a policeman.⁸⁵

⁸² A Field et al, (2021), “A Survey of Race, Racism, and Anti-Racism in NLP”, Association for Computational Linguistics, <https://aclanthology.org/2021.acl-long.149/>.

⁸³ T. Bolukbasi et al,(2016) ‘Man is to Computer Programmer as Woman is to Homemaker? Debiasing Word Embeddings’, NIPS, https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper_files/paper/2016/file/a486cd07e4ac3d270571622f4f316ec5-Paper.pdf

⁸⁴ S L Blodgett and B O’Connor (2017), ‘Racial Disparity in Natural Language Processing: A Case Study of Social Media African-American English’, 30 June 2017, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1707.00061.pdf>

⁸⁵ El País, (2021), ‘VeriPol, el polígrafo “inteligente” de la policía, puesto en cuestión por expertos en ética de los algoritmos’, 9 March 2021, <https://elpais.com/tecnologia/2021-03-08/veripol-el-poligrafo-inteligente-de-la-policia-puesto-en-cuestion-por-expertos-en-etica-de-los-algoritmos.html>

TVeriPol's creators say that they have not detected bias on the basis of ethnicity or gender in the use of the system.⁸⁶ One reason for this may be that the algorithm does not assess personal characteristics; it only scans inputs from the text an officer has put together. However, as mentioned above, specific words describing certain population groups, including ethnicity, are associated with false reports, meaning that the system is reproducing societal and structural biases represented in language.

There is no strict control over how the agents draft the text for each report. Allegedly, all officers using the tool receive relevant training, which covers certain methodological skills on what must be included. However, there is still a subjective approach to how they write the reports and previous research has found that not all of them have received the necessary training.

For example, officers are instructed to start nearly every sentence with the Spanish word "que", which roughly translates to "that". This means that the structure of the sentences included in the complaint does not correspond to the usual structure in the Spanish language. Also, each police officer might decide to add or leave out details that they consider unimportant, which could change the decision of the software.

Several officers complained about the lack of training on how to use the tool when it was introduced. Some said that the training only worked as a "theoretical approach" but did not "integrate" into their daily work,⁸⁷ while others said that they had never received the training needed.⁸⁸

As confirmed to Civio by the Technical Office of the Directorate General of Police, VeriPol ceased to be operational in October 2024. The Ministry of Interior pointed out the lack of validity in judicial proceedings as the main reason.⁸⁹

e) CAMINS (Mossos d'Esquadra, Catalonia)

Use: Individual risk assessment (not automated)

Created: 2017

CAMINS is a risk assessment protocol that the Catalanian police, the Mossos d'Esquadra, introduced in 2017, after a terrorist attack took place in the cities of Barcelona and Cambrils. The CAMINS analytical system does not contain mathematical models that make automated decisions. Rather, it is a type of risk assessment programme that generates data which could be used in a predictive model, or which could itself be automated.

⁸⁶ Quijano-Sánchez, L (2022), 'Applications of AI and Data Science in Policing: 7 years of collaborations with the Spanish Police', Lara Quijano-Sánchez, Ph.D by the Politechnic School of the Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, 25 January 2022, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=z8uBNNPtUmE>

⁸⁷ AlgorithmWatch (2020), 'Spanish police plan to extend use of its lie-detector while efficacy is unclear', 27 October 2020, <https://algorithmwatch.org/en/spain-police-veripol/>

⁸⁸ La Voz de Galicia. (2020), 'La comisaría de Vigo lleva dos años sin usar la "máquina de la verdad"', 30 August 2020, https://www.lavozdegalicia.es/noticia/vigo/vigo/2020/08/30/comisaria-vigo-lleva-dos-anos-usar-maquina-verdad/0003_202008V30C1991.htm

⁸⁹ Civio (2025): 'La Policía Nacional deja de usar VeriPol, su IA estrella para detectar denuncias falsas'. <https://civio.es/transparencia/2025/03/19/la-policia-nacional-deja-de-usar-veripol-su-ia-estrella-para-detectar-denuncias-falsas/>

In interviews, officers and an inspector in the Mossos d'Esquadra explained that the CAMINS risk assessment process consists of a fieldwork investigation through interviews with people who had some type of relationship with the individuals who committed the attack. The aim of CAMINS is to understand what factors led them to become 'radicalised' and to identify profiles for future analysis and prevention measures. An inspector in the Mossos d'Esquadra said:

"After analysing all the information contained therein, we apply an initial scheme which is based on a conceptual working model based on the combination of push and pull factors. The former predisposes people to violent radicalisation, while the latter attract people to a certain narrative. We come to certain conclusions, but the work does not follow scientific standards."⁹⁰

As a result, they started working with researchers from the University of Cordoba to create an analytical model that would adopt two methodological approaches: language analysis; and the identification of events in the lives of these individuals that may mark a turning point in their process of violent radicalisation. This was undertaken through "meta-analyses and the analysis of the university's datasets" of "psychological, social and behavioural points".

Among these data points are:

- age and gender;
- nationality;
- religion;
- education background;
- physical and mental health history;
- family relations during childhood and adolescence, including on family structure;
- cases of abuse;
- migration history and possible trauma resulting from it;
- time indicators for their first contact with violent 'extremist' narratives (in this case so-called 'jihadist'); or
- whether the individual is religious or not.

As the inspector in the Mossos d'Esquadra says:

A real-life example would be a young person who has never been into religion but suddenly shows an interest in the Muslim religion and has access to jihadist propaganda, thinking it is what Muslim religion is about. A possible intervention would be to provide a moderate view of Islam so that they understand what they are seeing. Another approach would be an intervention in the family".⁹¹

There is little meaningful substance behind these profiles of alleged 'radicalised' subjects, because there are not that many cases of violent 'radicalisation' to use for training. Looking for patterns to know what to expect in the future, via small amounts of data, leads to inefficient and inaccurate models. The inspector in the Mossos d'Esquadra argues:

⁹⁰ Interview date 18th October 2023.

⁹¹ Interview date 18th October 2023.

“We’re not planning to use mathematical models [for detecting radicalisation] because we’re not dealing with traditional profiling here. Violent radicalisation is too much of an internal and deep complex to be able to find profiles as easily. By ‘profile’ I mean something more substantial than talking of a man between 20 and 40 years old. We work on finding patterns that are useful to us but not in the sense of criminological profiling, as can be understood with serial killers or other cases”.⁹²

As is the case in other countries, individuals suspected of radicalising or committing a terrorist attack are born in Spain, in Catalonia in this case. According to the EU, around 60% of ‘jihadi’ attackers had the citizenship of the country where the attack took place.⁹³

f) Video Surveillance & image recognition (Community of Madrid)

Use: Monitoring and surveillance

Used by: Local Police

Purpose & outcome

In addition to location-focused and individual crime ‘prediction’ models, several localities in the Community of Madrid also use video surveillance systems that incorporate image recognition software. These systems have two purposes: automatic number plate recognition (ANPR) to monitor vehicles entering and leaving areas where crime has been recorded; and the identification of suspects involved in a crime.

The images are recorded by CCTV systems installed at strategic points in cities where the main entry and exit points of the city can be monitored. The recordings are managed and stored by the Local Police, but the National Police, Guardia Civil, immigration offices and other agencies may acquire access to them, for example, in judicial investigations.

Each vehicle entering and leaving the city is analysed by image recognition software. The software records the time the vehicle entered the city, left the city, where it travelled to and who it belongs to. The software also registers the number of people inside the vehicle, and scans their appearances. “We can make black-lists with the number plates,” said a police officer in Madrid.

Bosch Security provides the system to the Community of Madrid through the US-based firm Intelligent Security Systems (ISS).⁹⁴ The system allegedly does not identify people using face recognition, but the level of data that is registered through CCTV and video surveillance sometimes makes it possible to identify people. The software allows officers to search for people based on their appearance, including the colour of their hair, clothing and “facial features”, as explained by a member of Telecommunications and Modernisation at the Department for Innovation of a city in Madrid.⁹⁵ The system can also look for minors.

⁹² Entrevista realizada el 18 de octubre de 2023.

⁹³ European Parliament. ‘Jihadist terrorism in the EU since 2015’. 21 September 2021.

<https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/headlines/security/20180703STO07127/jihadist-terrorism-in-the-eu-since-2015>

⁹⁴ See the ‘Law Enforcement and Corrections’ webpage on the ISS website: <https://issivs.com/served-verticals/law-enforcement-and-corrections/> (last accessed 22 January 2025).

⁹⁵ Interview date 25th August 2023.

The software allows officers to search for gender, hair colour and age, as well as clothing.

The programme is not subject to data protection laws in the same way as face recognition surveillance systems because it supposedly does not identify people by cross-checking their images with another database holding pre-fixed identities. Nevertheless, it enables the identification of people according to the places they have passed through, their physical appearance or what they were wearing on a given day.

Impact

One of the former inspectors of the Rivas Vaciamadrid police station said that the local police did not collect specific data about decreasing crime rates in relation to the use of the system. He said it was the responsibility of the National Police to investigate criminal offences.

Despite this, he claimed that the tool offered “spectacular performance,” and that “there has been an increase in the effectiveness in the clarification of criminal acts, not that they are prevented, but there is a clarification”. However, no evidence has been provided to back up this claim, nor can it be independently verified.

This kind of software is also provided by other tech firms such as Avigilon, and has been used by the police in Spanish cities before. In 2019, El País described a programme used in Marbella (Andalusia) which analysed “‘unique facial factions’, upper and lower clothing colour, age, gender, hair colour and appearance” to identify suspects of crimes. This system also detected “unusual movements”.⁹⁶

⁹⁶ El País (2019), ‘Marbella, el mayor laboratorio de videovigilancia de España’, 22 November 2019, https://elpais.com/tecnologia/2019/11/21/actualidad/1574348695_231540.html

"False reports have been solved. Someone would tell us that they had been robbed in such and such a street, and once we looked at the recordings, we confirmed that they hadn't even passed that way," an inspector explained. Another automated algorithmic system, VeriPol, examined above, was designed for that task. "The [image recognition] system was activated during the last local festivities and people seemed to contain themselves more. There was an upward trend and now we haven't got worse. Shoplifting has actually gone down in monitored areas," he added. The article concluded that the cameras seemed to have a deterrent effect, although the hypothesis was theoretical and not upheld with data.⁹⁷

It remains unclear whether the system fulfils its purpose of decreasing criminality rates. There is no data available that links the installation of the program with an improvement in crime resolution.

⁹⁷ Ibid

4

Prisons: 'predictive' and profiling systems

So-called predictive, profiling and automated decision-making (ADM) systems have also been implemented in prisons in Spain, especially with the aim of profiling prisoners and assessing different levels of risk.

This section analyses two specific systems - one is used at a national level and the other is applied in the regional prisons of Catalonia.

a) DRAVY ('Detection of violent jihadist radicalisation')

Use: 'Prediction' and profiling of violent 'jihadist' ⁹⁸ radicalization

Created: 2018

Purpose & outcome

DRAVY is short for "detección de la radicalización violenta yihadista" - 'detection of violent jihadist radicalisation'. The individual risk assessment tool was created by the Spanish Secretary General of Penitentiary Institutions in 2018. It is supposed to identify prisoners allegedly undergoing a process of so-called 'jihadist' radicalisation and enable subsequent interventions. ⁹⁹

The first version of the tool was not automated. Prison evaluators analysed information about individuals manually to determine their risk level. The current version of the tool, now in its third version, however, does include an actuarial algorithm to predict the risk of 'radicalisation'.

Furthermore, the evaluators, working for the General Secretariat of Penitentiary Institutions also proposed that DRAVY should be used for "decision-making regarding prison treatment, as it quantifies the levels of propensity for violence and proselytising radicalisation shown by each individual at each point of assessment". This means that risk scores generated by DRAVY are used for making decisions about the level of individual monitoring of prisoners, defining security measures within facilities, and even probation decisions.¹⁰⁰ These are similar to the decision-making results provided by the RisCanvi algorithm used in Catalonia (explored in the following section).

⁹⁸ The terms 'terrorist', 'terrorism', 'Islamist', 'jihadist', 'extremism', 'extremist' and 'radicalisation' are ill-defined, imprecise and easily misused. As they routinely appear in laws, policies, government statements and academic research, however, they are used in this report for ease of reference. This does not imply that their use or definition by government institutions is endorsed. Per Amnesty UK (2023), This Is The Thought Police: The Prevent duty and its chilling effect on human rights', November 2023, <https://www.amnesty.org.uk/files/2023-11/Amnesty%20UK%20Prevent%20report%20%281%29.pdf>

⁹⁹ Senate (2019), 'Orden de servicio 3/2018', February 2018, <https://www.senado.es/web/expedientappendixblobervlet?legis=12&id1=119003&id2=1>

¹⁰⁰ Secretary General of Penitentiary Institutions, Ministry of Interior 'Construcción y validación de una herramienta de clasificación y de valoración del riesgo de radicalismo violento en el ámbito penitenciario', https://www.interior.gob.es/opencms/pdf/archivos-y-documentacion/documentacion-y-publicaciones/publicaciones-descargables/instituciones-penitenciarias/Construccion-y-validacion-de-una-herramienta-de-clasificacion-y-de-valoracion-del-riesgo-de-radicalismo-violento-en-el-ambito-penitenciario_126210405.pdf

DRAVY is not used to predict whether an individual will reoffend, with the creators of the algorithm stating that “violent recidivism is a very rare phenomenon prevalent in Spain” and as such, suggested that no predictor would be accurate enough for an individual risk assessment model.¹⁰¹ According to the National Statistics Institute, in the past 10 years, a total of 563 individuals have been convicted for acts related to terrorism or membership of terrorist groups.¹⁰² Recidivism for this particular state-defined crime type is low and varies — though an individual may reoffend for other types of criminal conduct.

Data & criteria

In the latest version of the model, the DRAVY tool draws on 63 risk factors that are grouped according to three different categories, depending on the ones assigned to the assessed prisoners: general violence exhibited at any time (especially extremist-ideological violence); ‘Islamist’ radicalisation; and changes in daily habits.¹⁰³

Not all those in prison are evaluated by DRAVY. It is reserved for those who have been convicted of terrorism or allegedly “displaying a propensity for terrorist radicalisation”. These are divided into three pre-defined groups:

- **Group A:** people convicted for membership or collaboration with terrorist groups;
- **Group B:** convicted for other reasons but who allegedly ‘radicalise’ others in prison, for example leading pressure groups and coercing them, or who enter prison for other crimes after having been released for their involvement in terrorist activities;
- **Group C:** people who are deemed vulnerable to recruitment for further ‘radicalisation’ (according to the evaluators) or who have incited or been involved in incidents with alleged radical interpretations.

The 63 risk variables in the latest version of DRAVY were tested on a sample of 537 prisoners. Out of this sample group, 281 prisoners belonged to one of the above-mentioned groups. The remaining 256 were Muslim prisoners who were used as a control group. Most of the control group (95%) were men around 36 years old. Alongside being assessed by the DRAVY risk algorithm, they were also manually assessed for risk of radicalisation by prison evaluators. The evaluators considered whether the risk factors included in the first version of the system were present or not, according to three cut-off points that classified the subjects into four levels of risk: no risk, low risk, medium risk and high risk.

DRAVY’s performance was assessed by analysing, with existing information, the risk profiles of 29 individuals. This group was selected according to their personal characteristics, mainly their alleged link to terrorism. Out of this group, six were recidivist prisoners of terrorism, and nine had previously been identified by the Centre for Intelligence against Terrorism and

101 González-Álvarez, J. L., Santos, J., Chiclana, S., & Pozuelo, F. (2021), ‘HERRAMIENTA PARA LA DETECCIÓN DE LA RADICALIZACIÓN VIOLENTA DE ETIOLOGÍA YIHADISTA (DRAVY) EN EL ÁMBITO PENITENCIARIO ESPAÑOL’, November 2021

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/355808392_ACTUALIZACION_DE_LA_HERRAMIENTA_PARA_LA_DETECCION_DE_LA_RADICALIZACION_VIOLENTA_DE_ETIOLOGIA_YIHADISTA_DRAVY_EN_EL_AMPITO_PENITENCIARIO_ESPANOL

102 National Statistics Institute (2023), ‘Convicted for ‘Terrorist organisations and groups and terrorist crimes’’, retrieved in October 2023 from: <https://www.ine.es/up/NvD9x6p8i40>

103 González-Álvarez, J. L., Santos-Hermoso, J., Gómez, Á., López-Novo, J. L., Buquerín-Pascual, S., Pozuelo-Rubio, F., Fernández-Gómez, C., & Chiclana, S. (2024). A Theoretical, Empirical, and Methodologically Based Instrument to Assess the Risk of Violent Jihadist Radicalization in Prisons: The DRAVY-3. *Terrorism and Political Violence*, 36(3), 283-299. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09546553.2022.2145194>

Organised Crime as being of interest for monitoring outside prison. The database used for validating the indicators that compose the system included the following variables: gender, age, country of birth and nationality.¹⁰⁴

The creators of DRAVY concluded that the instrument's performance and accuracy for detecting 'jihadist' radicalisation was "adequate".¹⁰⁵ They conducted a statistical assessment based on sensitivity and specificity. "Sensitivity" refers to the true positive rate: that is, the rate at which a positive prediction is accurate ("true"). "Specificity" refers to the true negative rate: the rate at which a negative prediction is accurate. The terms true positive, false negative, true negative and false positive are explained in the table below using the example of people being examined for sickness.¹⁰⁶

The assessment carried out by the creators of DRAVY gave the system a sensitivity rate of almost 83%. That is, for every 10 people who would go on to become radicalised, eight of them would have been assessed as likely to become radicalised. Two of those ten would have received a false negative rating from the system: it would have incorrectly assessed them as not likely to become radicalised.

The assessment gave DRAVY a specificity rate of almost 64%. For every ten people who did not become radicalised, six of them would have been accurately considered low-risk subjects and would not radicalise at any point (true negatives). The other four would have wrongly been assessed as low risk (false positives).

This is a very high number of false positives. It means that nearly half of people assessed by the system will unduly receive stricter treatment and tougher living conditions in prison.

Generally, individuals who are considered to radicalise in prisons in Spain are considered as such because they share socio-demographic characteristics with 'jihadists' who were arrested, convicted or killed. Most of them are men around 28 or 29 years old. The reference religion is Islam, "but conversion processes can occur in prisoners with a cultural or family background of other religious traditions, leading to jihadist radicalisation if conditions are favourable — especially, exposure to jihadist propaganda or interaction with other radicalisation agents".¹⁰⁷

When it comes to radicalisation, even though the numbers show that people who radicalise in Spain are people who are actually born in the country, non-nationals are disproportionately targeted by predictive and risk assessment models. Moroccans are the most studied collective in this case.¹⁰⁸ Also when it comes to DRAVY — half of the individuals (48,5%) included in the sample used to validate the algorithm were of Moroccan descent. Almost 30% were Spaniards and 8% were from Algeria.¹⁰⁹

¹⁰⁴ Secretary General of Penitentiary Institutions, Ministry of Interior (2021), 'Construcción y validación de una herramienta de clasificación y de valoración del riesgo de radicalismo violento en el ámbito penitenciario', https://www.interior.gob.es/opencms/pdf/archivos-y-documentacion/documentacion-y-publicaciones/publicaciones-descargables/instituciones-penitenciarias/Construccion-y-validacion-de-una-herramienta-de-clasificacion-y-de-valoracion-del-riesgo-de-radicalismo-violento-en-el-ambito-penitenciario_126210405.pdf

¹⁰⁵ The creators of DRAVY assigned the model an AUC (area under the curve) of 0.78; sensitivity (true positive rate) of 82.75%; and specificity of 63.80% (true negative rate).

¹⁰⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sensitivity_and_specificity

¹⁰⁷ Real Instituto Elcano (2018), 'Yihadismo y prisiones: un análisis del caso español', 14 November 2018, <https://www.realinstitutoelcano.org/analisis/yihadismo-y-prisiones-un-analisis-del-caso-espanol/>

¹⁰⁸ Real Instituto Elcano (2018), 'Marroquíes y segundas generaciones entre los yihadistas en España', 27 April 2018, <https://www.realinstitutoelcano.org/analisis/marroquies-y-segundas-generaciones-entre-los-yihadistas-en-espana/>

¹⁰⁹ Secretary General of Penitentiary Institutions, Ministry of Interior, 'Construcción y validación de una herramienta de clasificación y de valoración del riesgo de radicalismo violento en el ámbito penitenciario', https://www.interior.gob.es/opencms/pdf/archivos-y-documentacion/documentacion-y-publicaciones/publicaciones-descargables/instituciones-penitenciarias/Construccion-y-validacion-de-una-herramienta-de-clasificacion-y-de-valoracion-del-riesgo-de-radicalismo-violento-en-el-ambito-penitenciario_126210405.pdf

Impact

One of the most critical studies on the use of DRAVY is not directed towards the tool itself but at the field in which it is applied. It considers that its objective, rather than neutralising the radicalisation of prisoners, may actually enhance it: “Attempts to define radicalisation in absolute terms have revealed constant conflicts in trying to establish the relationship between radicalism and violence, and between thought and action, which has made it very difficult to establish successful functional policies”.¹¹⁰

The authors of that study criticise the construction of the algorithm, suggesting it is based on “risk factors that refer to their morality, ideology or religion”. They say it “detaches the existence of the radical from external behaviour and poses the danger as derived exclusively from their ideas, worldview and morality, i.e. their ideological position”.¹¹¹

This can be seen in how many of DRAVY’s variables related to risk of radicalisation identify a subjective separation between cultures. One of them, for example, refers to the use of the terms “you” and “we” by prisoners, or whether they have said that they feel “vulnerable” or “weak” without specifying a reason.¹¹²

The major concern this raises is that obtaining a high DRAVY risk score determines the treatment people will receive in prison. For example: isolation or solitary confinement, control and monitoring measures, the imposition of a tougher regime in prison, or even a longer sentence.

The study notes that Spain’s rules on radicalisation in prisons, introduced in 2018, interpret radicalisation in a way that “opens up two possible lines of action”. On the one hand, the “pursuit of re-education and social reintegration in a broad sense.” On the other hand, is long-term isolation and imprisonment.”.¹¹³

The authors conclude:

“It’s especially concerning that under a preventive logic — that is, acting against a threat that is not yet a threat — the figure of the radical is constructed on the basis of factors which, being purely subjective, have a direct impact on the morality, ideology and religiosity of the inmate.”.

As the main purpose of DRAVY is for assessing ‘jihadist’ radicalisation, it is fundamentally discriminatory on the basis that it is almost exclusively focused on Muslims and people from Muslim backgrounds. The system is set up to target ‘jihadism’, a term that itself relies on discriminatory Western stereotypes.

¹¹⁰ Aguerri, J. C., & Abad, C. F. (2021), ‘La orden de servicios 3/2018: ¿un instrumento para medir el riesgo de radicalismo violento en prisión?’, *Estudios Penales y Criminológicos*, 41, 361-413, <https://revistas.usc.gal/index.php/epc/article/view/67241>

¹¹¹ Ibid

¹¹² González-Álvarez, J. L., Santos-Hermoso, J., Gómez, Á., López-Novo, J. L., Buquerín-Pascual, S., Pozuelo-Rubio, F., Fernández-Gómez, C., & Chiclana, S. (2022), ‘A Theoretical, empirical, and methodologically based instrument to assess the risk of violent Jihadist radicalization in prisons: The DRAVY-3’, *Terrorism and Political Violence*, 1-17, 9 December 2022, <https://blogs.uned.es/idenfusion/wp-content/uploads/sites/553/2024/09/Gonzalez-Alvarez-et-al.-2022-DRAVY-3.pdf>

¹¹³ Aguerri, J. C., & Abad, C. F. (2021), ‘La orden de servicios 3/2018: ¿un instrumento para medir el riesgo de radicalismo violento en prisión?’, *Estudios Penales y Criminológicos*, 41, 361-413, <https://revistas.usc.gal/index.php/epc/article/view/67241>

As with other systems investigated in this report, following four months of inquiries, the Ministry of Interior denied our requests to interview the authors of the studies that validate the model. In 2023, most of the authors were working for the State Secretary for Security, as well as the Secretary General of Penitentiary Institutions.

b) RISCANVI (Department of Justice, Catalonia)

Use: Prison recidivism risk assessment system

Created: 2010

Purpose & outcome

RisCanvi was introduced to the regional prisons of Catalonia in 2010. The Catalanian Department of Justice's intention was to incorporate an algorithmic risk assessment system that would aid their teams in "predicting" the risk of recidivism among the prison population. RisCanvi consists of a complex protocol instead of a single questionnaire.

At a fixed frequency, usually every six months, individuals in prisons are interviewed by a team of professionals from the Department of Justice. The team is composed of around 750 people from different fields, including psychologists, social workers, educators and legal criminologists. This assessment team can decide whether to shorten the period between each prisoner's evaluation. The results of these interviews are then fed into the RisCanvi algorithm, which produces a risk score: low, medium or high.

To do so, RisCanvi uses a deterministic statistical model that analyses a large set of data points. There are two versions of the model: RisCanvi-S (which stands for the *screening* model) and RisCanvi-C (referring to the *complete* model). RisCanvi-S is a model consisting of 10 elements that is applied to the entire prison population. RisCanvi-C has 43 elements and is little-used, due to time limitations. RisCanvi-C is mainly used when the *screening* model RisCanvi-S assigns somebody a high risk, or when the evaluators feel the need to undertake an exhaustive assessment of the person.¹¹⁴

The shorter RisCanvi-S takes into account the following information about a person when 'predicting' their risk of recidivism:

- If the person has a history of violence and from what age;
- their financial situation; and
- if they have family or social support.

RisCanvi-S also analyses whether an individual has a history of substance or alcohol use.

¹¹⁴ Andrés-Pueyo, A., Arbach-Lucioni, K., & Redondo, S. (2018), 'The RisCanvi: a new tool for assessing risk for violence in prison and recidivism'. Handbook of recidivism risk/needs assessment tools, 255-268. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/9781119184256.ch13>

The complete RisCanvi-C model integrates some of these risk factors as well as stressing other parameters such as:

- Role of violence in their offence;
- the prisoner's educational background;
- their employment history;
- social relationships and associations; and
- mental health conditions or personality disorders.

RisCanvi-C also analyses in further depth the offender's relationships with their friends and family; and in particular whether any of these relations display a criminal history.

In addition to each of the different data points, both RisCanvi-S and RisCanvi-C draw on the following four parameters that are present in all evaluations: age, gender, nationality, and type of detention (whether the person being assessed has been convicted or pending trial). These are fixed variables that apply regardless of the version used.

Although the weightings for the fixed variables remain the same, the weightings for the other data points vary depending on which criteria is being analysed by the algorithm. The descriptions of the variables and their weightings within the system are publicly available.¹¹⁵

The risk score generated by the algorithm does not only correspond to general recidivism, but also to a variety of other behaviours and scenarios. These include:

- violent recidivism;
- self-inflicted harm;
- violence to other colleagues or inside the facilities; and
- breaking of licence.

From the risk score generated by combining these factors, the assessment department then decides what conditions to impose, such as eligibility for transfer to another prison, or for parole. In some cases, the risk scores are also included in reports received by judges when making decisions on release from prison.

According to the Head of the Rehabilitation Service of the Directorate General of Penitentiary Affairs, the risk score generated by the algorithm matches the conclusion of the assessment team "in 95% of cases, if not more".¹¹⁶

RisCanvi was mainly created by one of the psychologists who developed the VioGén system. They largely based the design of the algorithm on the Canadian system Level of Service Inventory-Revised (LSIR).¹¹⁷ RisCanvi's creators have denied that the Catalan system is similar to the COMPAS risk assessment tool used in the US, which was found to produce racist and inaccurate assessments.¹¹⁸

¹¹⁵ Justice Department of the Catalan Generalitat (2019), 'Manual d'aplicació del protocol de valoració RisCanvi'.

<https://repositori.justicia.gencat.cat/bitstream/handle/20.500.14226/1320/manual-aplicacio-protocol-avaluacio-riscanvi.pdf>.

¹¹⁶ AlgorithmWatch (2021), 'In Catalonia, the RisCanvi algorithm helps decide whether inmates are paroled', 25 May 2021.

<https://algorithmwatch.org/en/riscanvi/>

¹¹⁷ Lemay, M (2019), 'Understanding Canada's Algorithmic Impact Assessment', 11 June 2019 Tool,

<https://towardsdatascience.com/understanding-canadas-algorithmic-impact-assessment-tool-cd0d3c8cafab>

¹¹⁸ Pro Publica (2016), 'Machine Bias', 23 May 2016, <https://www.propublica.org/article/machine-bias-risk-assessments-in-criminal-sentencing>

Data & criteria

In 2021, the head of the Directorate General of Penitentiary Affairs said that RisCanvi was used to assess risk at an individual level. This, they argued, made it unnecessary to collect aggregated data on people assessed by it in order to evaluate the algorithm.¹¹⁹ This means that no data is actively collected on how RisCanvi works according to the four fixed variables of age, gender, nationality or type of detention.

According to the 2020 official recidivism rate report, most of the individuals (70.8%) evaluated by RisCanvi are given a low score. The latest official report on recidivism rates shows that the general rate in 2020 was 21.1%. Among men, it stood at 21.2%, while for women it was 20%.¹²⁰

In terms of nationality, available data shows that 20.4% of Spanish prisoners re-offend; 24.1% from the EU; 3.2% from the rest of Europe; 21.1% from the Maghreb; 26.1% from the rest of Africa; 1.59% from South and Central America; and 27.6% from Asia. As of today, the recidivism rates for Spaniards and other nationalities are practically equal: 20.4% for the former and 22.2% for the latter.

The official 2014 report on recidivism rates provided data on the performance and accuracy of RisCanvi. It said the system is able to correctly flag almost eight out of 10 people who reoffend (true positives). The two remaining would be false negatives, i.e. persons who did reoffend but were not signalled as at risk of reoffending by the programme. The system would also be able, according to the same data, to accurately identify as non-recidivists 6 out of 10 people (true negatives). The remaining 4 people would be considered false positives: individuals who did not subsequently reoffend but that were marked by the system as medium or high risk.¹²¹

Impact

According to the managers, the rate of false positives is not among their priorities. They believe that the false negatives are the greater issue, i.e. individuals who are assigned a low-risk score but turn out to be more dangerous than first evaluated. “Of a false negative (...) everyone becomes aware. It hits the legitimacy of the system; it’s a political issue. A false positive is an injustice for the inmate. But who finds out? Them, their family... No one else”, a magistrate at the Provincial Court of Girona (Catalonia) told the newspaper La Vanguardia in 2021.¹²² The fact that prisoners can be wrongly labelled as high risk, leading to punitive consequences, is a serious injustice. It also lays bare the lack of accountability in the use of the system.

Several studies that seek to prove the algorithm’s success have focused on its performance according to age, nationality, and gender. A recent study by the Catalanian Centre for Legal Studies and Specialized Training concludes: “The models are more accurate for foreigners

119 AlgorithmWatch (2021), ‘In Catalonia, the RisCanvi algorithm helps decide whether inmates are paroled’, 25 May 2021, <https://algorithmwatch.org/en/riscanvi/>

120 Catalanian Legal Studies and Specialized Formation Centre (2023), ‘Tasa de reincidencia penitenciaria’, <https://repositori.justicia.gencat.cat/handle/20.500.14226/638#page=1>

121 The sensitivity of the algorithm is 77%, while the specificity is 57%.

122 La Vanguardia (2021), ‘Un algoritmo impreciso condiciona la libertad de los presos’, 7 December 2021, <https://www.lavanguardia.com/vida/20211206/7888727/algoritmo-sirve-denegar-permisos-presos-pese-fallos.html>

foreigners than Spanish nationals and there is no significant difference in age sub-groups". The study focused on RisCanvi's performance according to age and nationality.¹²³ The authors stated: "There is a disparity in the average number of evaluations which shows that a lower number of evaluations are undertaken on average for foreigners and older prisoners".

This means that prisoners with Spanish citizenship are evaluated much more frequently than 'foreigners' — which also means that their risk status is more likely to change from high to low. Their prison sentence is thus more likely to be modified, as opposed to non-Spanish.

Another study evaluated the data points used in RisCanvi according to other socio-economic characteristics. The study found that higher risk scores are given to recidivists with a history of unstable employment and finances, as well as in some cases those without family or social support and/or family members or parents with a criminal history.¹²⁴ One of the algorithm's creators stated that the risk level of an Afghan individual would not be evaluated equally if he was illiterate or an industrial engineer.¹²⁵

A smaller statistical analysis of RisCanvi's results and performance emphasises that the algorithm "offers good results when detecting non-reoffenders" but performs "very poorly" when predicting recidivism.¹²⁶ In line with other experiments, the analysis demonstrated that offenders with Spanish nationality receive higher risk scores than non-nationals. The study also found that mental health issues and a history of substance use "clearly increases the [predicted] recidivism rate".

Given that risk scores generated by RisCanvi are often provided to judges to support parole decisions, there is a general request among legal representatives for transparency with regards to the role RisCanvi plays in judicial processes, such as in decisions related to licence benefits, parole and more.

It remains unclear to what extent automated systems influence judicial processes generally. Previous academic literature shows that, on the one hand, in many cases judges do not follow algorithmic risk assessments if they don't align with their own perspective.¹²⁷ For example, a racist judge may discredit the algorithm's risk score if it differs from their own judgement in a case with somebody from a racially minoritised background. Another case study found that the majority of participants maintained their original decision unless the algorithm predicted that the person would reoffend, in which case they changed their answer to align with the system.¹²⁸

¹²³ Karimi-Haghighi, M., & Castillo, C (2021), 'Efficiency and fairness in recurring data-driven risk assessments of violent recidivism', In Proceedings of the 36th Annual ACM Symposium on Applied Computing (pp. 994-1002), March 2021

https://chato.cl/papers/karimi_haghighi_castillo_2021_efficiency_fairness_temporal_recurring_

¹²⁴ Ibid

¹²⁵ AlgorithmWatch (2021), 'In Catalonia, the RisCanvi algorithm helps decide whether inmates are paroled', 25 May 2021,

<https://algorithmwatch.org/en/riscanvi/>

¹²⁶ Briz-Redón, A., & Montes, F. (2022), 'Análisis de los resultados del protocolo RisCanvi', Universidad de Valencia, October 2022

<https://www.uv.es/montes/informe%20riscanvi/informe.pdf>

¹²⁷ Green, B., & Chen, Y. (2019). The principles and limits of algorithm-in-the-loop decision making. Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction, 3(CSCW), 1-24, <https://scholar.harvard.edu/files/bggreen/files/19-cscw.pdf>

5

Databases

In addition to the ADM and AI systems outlined in this report, law enforcement authorities also use and rely on databases to make decisions. This section analyses key information sources and databases used by the Policia Nacional. Understanding their functions and the origins of the information they contain is a necessary step in understanding whether they jeopardise or infringe on people's rights.

These databases are only supposed to be accessed by authorised officers due to data protection and privacy laws. Accessing information about these databases and information sources is difficult because they are usually composed of personal and sensitive information about groups of people.

Many ADM systems — including those mentioned in this report — are criticised for reinforcing bias and harming people due to malfunctioning design, production or usage. However, bias can occur outside of poor design and implementation of an algorithm. Discrimination can also arise from databases because of the origin and type of data they contain. It is important to emphasise that the use of databases alone can lead to discriminatory practices.¹²⁹ For instance, if outdated information is held about an individual on a database, it could lead to them being wrongly arrested. In Spain, migrants have been erroneously detained because their records on databases managed by law enforcement authorities and civil servants were not properly updated.

This section explores three main databases used in Spain by police and law enforcement authorities:

- **ABIS** (Automated Biometric Identification System, previously known as SAID);
- **ADEXTTRA** (foreigner registration database); and
- **ADPASFIL** (passports and migration database).

These databases cover a wide range of population groups and contain sensitive information ranging from fingerprints to criminal history to images of detainees. Some of them power AI systems, for example face recognition systems used by the National Police (see section on ABIS).

¹²⁹ Valdivia, A., & Tazzioli, M. (2023, June). Datafication Genealogies beyond Algorithmic Fairness: Making Up Racialised Subjects. In Proceedings of the 2023 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency (pp. 840-850). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3593013.3594047>

Name of the database	Aim	Group of people affected	Data stored	Used for
ABIS	To store fingerprints	Detainees for criminal offences and migrants detained by Spanish migration law	Alphanumeric (ID, name and surnames, gender, etc.), biometrics and images	Police investigation
ADEXTTRA	To store bureaucratic reports and documents of migrants	Migrants (including minors) in the Spanish territory	Alphanumeric (name and surnames, gender, job position, etc.), biometrics, audios and images	Administrative checks on migration status and police investigation
ADPASFIL	To store passport information	Spanish citizens issuing a passport, asylum seekers and stateless individuals	Alphanumeric (ID, name and surnames, address, nationality), biometrics and images	Administrative checks, checks on migration status and police investigation

Table 1: Relevant databases used by the Policía Nacional.

ABIS, ADEXTTRA and ASPASFIL are national databases, which means they are not interoperable and are not linked with other European databases, such as EURODAC,¹³⁰ ETIAS¹³¹ or the Entry/Exit System (EES¹³²).¹³³

Nevertheless, the information contained in these databases is shared with law enforcement authorities from other EU Member States and public administrations who request access — such as the prosecution authorities, Social Security authorities or the Ministries of Presidency or Foreign Affairs.

¹³⁰ Used to store biometric and biographic data taken from asylum applicants, undocumented migrants and people facing deportation.

¹³¹ The European Travel Information and Authorisation System, ETIAS, will be used to process and store “travel authorisation” applications from non-EU nationals that wish to visit the Schengen area, and who do not require a visa to do so.

¹³² The Entry/Exit System will be used for the biometric registration of all Schengen area external border crossings by non-EU nationals.

¹³³ Statewatch. “Frontex and interoperable databases. Knowledge as power?”. February 2023, <https://www.statewatch.org/media/3725/frontex-and-interoperable-databases-report.pdf>

a) ABIS (Automated Biometric Identification System)

Automated Biometric Identification System (ABIS) is an international standard that refers to programs that perform facial or other biometric recognition, such as on fingerprints, and the name of the corresponding database held by Spanish police. In Spain, this database powers a face recognition software provided by the French company Thales, which is widely known in the biometric industry.¹³⁴

The Spanish police use their algorithm Cogent to identify people contained in the ABIS database, previously named SAID. Changed its name to ABIS shortly after the Cogent program was incorporated.¹³⁵ The previous initials stood for Sistema Automático de Identificación Dactilar ('Automatic System for Fingerprint Identification'). It contained mostly fingerprints of detained persons. All law enforcement authorities had access to it: National Police, Civil Guard, the Ertzaintza, the Mossos D'Esquadra and the Regional Police of Navarra. Data was also shared with European law enforcement agencies.

The ABIS database contains around five million photographs of people who have been detained or flagged as suspects by security forces. These are frontal facial images taken by the National Police and Civil Guard.

The office for Information and Communication Systems for Security at the Ministry of Interior says that the database does not register demographic data: "The ABIS database does not use demographic diversity calibrations and works with a matching system that uses only the comparison of eye and nose data, regardless of the nationality of the subject in the images, which is not included in the processing".¹³⁶

Biometric data of both adults and minors is registered, regardless of whether they are Spanish citizens or not. Allegedly, there is no international transfer of data about minors, although the Ministry of Interior states that "police organisations from other countries" and "international organisations" are among the categories of possible recipients.¹³⁷

In most cases, fingerprints are collected and registered digitally by the 'live scan' protocol — the same used by European databases like EURODAC. Around 5% of fingerprints included in the database are not introduced through this system, which means they are inked and scanned manually. This is the case in border posts located in places like the Canary Islands that do not have digital access. This means that the quality of this data is not as high as data obtained through live scanning and can lead to misidentification or no identification at all.

The whole system — the Cogent computer program along with the ABIS database — is used for the prevention, investigation and detection of criminal offences, and particularly for identifying suspects involved. This includes prevention of threats to public security, as stated by the Ministry of Interior.¹³⁸ The ABIS system can combine its own files with INTERPOL's Face Recognition System (IFRS),¹³⁹ fuelled by the information sent by almost 180 countries.

¹²⁸ Valdivia, A., Aradau, C., Blanke, T., & Perret, S. (2022), 'Neither opaque nor transparent: A transdisciplinary methodology to investigate datafication at the EU borders'. *Big Data & Society*, 9(2), 20539517221124586. 21 September 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1177/20539517221124586>.

¹³⁵ According to answers received through the submission of FOIA requests.

¹³⁶ Ibid

¹³⁷ Ministry of Interior (2023), 'Registro de actividad de tratamientos del Ministerio del Interior', Updated October 2023,

<https://transparencia.gob.es/transparencia/dam/jcr:b3eb17bc-b1a7-4092-9c99-f11f62d868ae/20241211%20Inventario%20de%20Actividades%20de%20Tratamiento%20del%20Ministerio%20del%20Interior.pdf>

¹³⁸ According to answers received through the submission of FOIA requests.

¹³⁹ Interpol, 'Facial recognition', <https://www.interpol.int/How-we-work/Forensics/Facial-Recognition>

All types of images are passed through the ABIS system for police to check. An example given by the Scientific Police, who work with the face recognition software, is that of video footage of a bank robbery. Apparently, these images can be sent to the police to run through their software. The system takes in the images and, after cross-checking with the database, offers a list of around 40 to 50 candidates for potential matches. The relevant officer then has to check the options and decide whether the person they are seeking matches any of the results.¹⁴⁰

Unlike a live facial recognition system, the Cogent algorithm is used to perform a retrospective search. This circumvents the restrictions on live face recognition in the EU AI Act, a new landmark law attempting to regulate AI and prohibit some of the most harmful uses.¹⁴¹ However, the Spanish Data Protection Authority was not consulted when the system was first tested, and in 2023 still had to assess whether the Cogent algorithm can be used this way.¹⁴²

The new ABIS database was fed with the information that was contained in the predecessor SAID database. Now, as well as fingerprints, it also includes photographs of these people and additional suspects gathered by the police. There are widespread international calls for a ban on the use of face recognition by the police — the most prominent being the Reclaim Your Face campaign¹⁴³ — as it is considered a flawed technology that increases the risk of people being wrongfully detained.

b) ADEXTTRA (Foreigner registration database)

ADEXTTRA is the database holding information about foreign citizens, non-EU citizens with an irregular status or Spanish citizens affected by immigration laws. The police refer to this database when conducting stops and identity checks, for example to check someone's legal status.

In ADEXTTRA, the police register a person's name, date and place of birth, gender, names of their parents, telephone number and email. Police also register ID and passport number, social security number and their Foreigner Identification Number (known in Spain as NIE). This number is essentially an ID for non-nationals who have residence in a country.

Along with this data, police collect an extensive list of socio-economic information: nationality, marital status, profession and work activities, if the individual has any properties and holdings, their income and revenues, information about cohabitation and extrajudicial detentions, conduct and criminal history. The database also contains a large quantity of biometric data. The police keep photographs and other images about the individual, and fingerprints and voice samples.

¹⁴⁰ RTVE (2023) 'Reconocimiento facial', 2 October 2023, <https://www.rtve.es/play/audios/memoria-de-delfin/reconocimiento-facial-1-hora/6977564/>

¹⁴¹ Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1689/oj/eng>

¹⁴² Business Insider(2022), 'Interior reconoce que no ha consultado a la AEPD sobre el algoritmo de reconocimiento facial que está entrenando para la policía', 26 December 2022, www.businessinsider.es/interior-no-ha-consultado-aepd-antes-construir-ia-policia-1173474

¹⁴³ Reclaim Your Face: <https://reclaimyourface.eu/>

ADEXTTRA also collects data about minors, mostly biometric and identifiable, plus information about the place where the child is living (this includes shelters and mention of the public organisation taking care of them) and the people with whom they arrived in the country. In the case of minors, they also register physical and physiological data, such as forensic reports that seek to determine their age or whether they have tattoos or “physical and psychological marks and impairments”.¹⁴⁴

Information contained in ADEXTTRA is shared with other police departments and every public administration office that intervenes in migration bureaucracy. Information relating to adults is also transferred to organisations such as Interpol and Europol, or to EU police databases such as the Schengen Information System. Data about minors is shared with other European immigration offices or those responsible for unaccompanied minors.

ADEXTTRA is consulted by the Immigration Office’s systems to update information on small boats and the number of migrants they carry, other types of “illegal immigration movements”, as well as information about processes involving repatriated minors, minors in custody, or other non-Spanish national status procedures, such as deportations and the return of migrants to their country of origin.¹⁴⁵

As mentioned above, ADEXTTRA is also used to identify migrants and check their status in the country. The police will stop people with a supposed ‘foreign’ appearance and ask for their documentation. Police have the capacity to arrest someone and take them into custody if they believe that the documentary evidence presented is inadequate — for example, photocopies — or if they believe it may be forged (which is sometimes a subjective decision).

During this process, verifications include checking the latest updates to a person’s information on ADEXTTRA. Documents are displayed in chronological order, so it may not be immediately apparent to the officer that the person’s status is legal. This means that an officer may presume a person’s situation is illegal and arrest them, instead of checking the database more thoroughly.

As stated by a member of the Government Delegation:

“Several bodies are involved in expulsions: the police, the government delegation, and even the brigade, depending on the case. So often the data is not recorded in ADEXTTRA (...) Sometimes we find that the police open a file on a person and when it gets to us it appears as if they have been granted a permit. The police did not know that they had been granted a permit because they cannot check it, so they send us an expulsion that we have to file (...) This happens very often, that is, a lot”.¹⁴⁶

¹⁴⁴ Ministry of Interior. ‘Registro de actividad de tratamientos del Ministerio del Interior’. Updated October 2023, <https://transparencia.gob.es/transparencia/dam/jcr:b3eb17bc-b1a7-4092-9c99-f11f62d868ae/20241211%20Inventario%20de%20Actividades%20de%20Tratamiento%20del%20Ministerio%20del%20Interior.pdf>

¹⁴⁵ Dirección General de la Policía. ‘Predisposiciones técnicas para la contratación de servicios de mantenimiento de aplicaciones policiales 2020-2022’, <https://contrataciondelestado.es/wps/wcm/connect/070db1fd-c9b7-4b0d-ae91-b9ac6c6ecaab/DOC20200818140525PPT+v2+0.pdf?MOD=AJPERES>

¹⁴⁶ Sainz de la Maza Quintanal, E. (2015), “‘Ultima ratio’: el proceso de expulsión de inmigrantes en situación irregular en España”, <https://docta.ucm.es/entities/publication/769b2a6c-8db4-4e2f-8f8e-623cb7c9ce6c>

Police officers interviewed confirm this tendency:

“Like any other database this one has flaws. Not necessarily the last procedure is the one that currently corresponds to the person; you have to look at all procedures. If all of them have expired, then that person would be in an irregular situation, but if any of them has been granted or is in the process of doing so within the last three months, that person cannot be arrested”.¹⁴⁷

Along with checks that are incomplete or conducted incorrectly, failure to update the database properly also leads to discriminatory outcomes for legally-resident people. For instance, in one case, a woman was wrongly detained for irregular status. The police offered her to legalise her situation in the country if she provided information about a case on drug trafficking and illegal possession of weapons. She did so, but this transaction was never included in ADEXTTRA. Therefore, the next time she was stopped by the police, they detained her illegally, ignoring all the previous occurrences.

c) ADPASFIL (Passports and migration database)

ADPASFIL contains data on the issuance of passports. Alongside ADEXTTRA, it is the other main database in Spain for managing sensitive data on undocumented persons, stateless persons or people who have been granted the right of asylum. As such, ADPASFIL processes biometric and other information on migrants.

The database consists of the following identifying data: full name, date and birthplace, parents name, sex, nationality, ID number (if they have one), nationality, photograph, signature and fingerprints. Individuals included in ADPASFIL can also appear in other databases, such as ABIS or ADEXTTRA.

When deemed appropriate, all this information is shared and cross-checked with international organisations such as Interpol and Europol, SIS II and the European Union.

The Ministry of Interior intends to make ADPASFIL and other databases, such as ADEXTTRA, interoperable so that biometric information is more accessible to other systems, such as the register for missing persons.¹⁴⁸

ADPASFIL complements the databases mentioned above - ABIS and ADEXTTRA - with regards to the information handled by the Immigration Office on the status of migrants. As is the case with ADEXTTRA, it can sometimes be problematic for people regularising their status in Spain to have their situation correctly updated on the ADPASFIL database.

¹⁴⁷ Ibid

¹⁴⁸ Ministry of Interior, 'I Plan Estratégico en Materia de Personas Desaparecidas 2022-2024', https://www.lamoncloa.gob.es/serviciosdeprensa/notasprensa/interior/Documents/2022/090322_I_Plan_Estrategico_Personas_Desaparecidas_22-24.pdf

6

Conclusions

This report has identified and analysed some of the main rule-based and automated decision-making systems and databases used by law enforcement and criminal justice authorities in Spain. It is clear that there is a predisposition by different police forces towards implementing automated and data-based systems for crime 'prediction' and profiling. These systems influence their decisions and actions, with a range of different effects on people. The use of these systems in the criminal legal system has significant consequences for people's imprisonment and probation.

The consequences and impact of these systems are clear: the criminalisation of certain communities, and discrimination against the people and groups who are targeted. There is also a consistent lack of transparency about the use of the systems, including the data they use, how they are used, their impact and who is impacted by them, and as a result, minimal opportunity for accountability.

Criminalisation

ADM systems are used by dozens of localities across Spain to influence law enforcement surveillance and patrols, leading to increased policing in those areas and of those groups and communities, and likely to result in increased criminalisation of those communities.

Police use algorithmic systems to assess victims of crime, sometimes with minimal human oversight or intervention: police officers mostly rely on VioGén automated assessments cases, according to independent research. Police also use automated systems to assess victims and perpetrators of gender-based violence, for the purpose of deciding on what level of monitoring to assign. Law enforcement authorities use machine-learning algorithms to assess crime reports and decide whether to investigate.

Law enforcement and prisons across Spain also use individual risk assessment tools to assess people, such as their likelihood of 'jihadist' radicalisation or committing terrorism. The DRAYV algorithmic system predictions influence the conditions an individual is held in in prison, and probation decisions. Similarly, RisCanvi predictions are used to determine an individual's prison conditions, whether they are ready for parole, and are even given to judges to inform probation decisions.

The police databases are powering face recognition systems and are systematically used to gather and store evidence about subjects in Spanish territory. The wrong implementation of these digital records could result in a person being illegally detained.

Discrimination

Law enforcement and criminal justice is a sphere in which already there are significant structural and institutional prejudices towards racialised communities and other targeted groups. This means that data-based, automated and algorithmic systems implemented in this context could reproduce and amplify these dynamics by over-policing certain areas in a city or automating increased stigmatisation towards certain groups and communities.

Studies show that police in Spain already disproportionately stop and search people based on their racial, ethnic, or religious appearance,¹⁴⁹ while police have acknowledged that their use of location-focused 'prediction' systems like EuroCop is likely to lead to the targeting of poorer areas.

Risk assessment systems like VioGén and EPV-R rely on whether an alleged or known offender is a 'foreigner' as an influencing factor in the assessment. EPV-R even profiles people from a 'migration background' as more likely than someone from the 'West' to commit an offence. The sexual aggressors profiling by the Spanish National Police also profiles 'foreigners' and 'non-Spaniards' as more likely to commit crimes.

DRAVY was tested using Muslim prisoners as the control group, and Moroccans make up almost half of all those targeted, which means that it could present bias towards this population. It also has an acknowledged false positive rate of 40%. 'Foreigners' are assessed less often by RisCanvi and have less opportunity to lower their risk score than nationals.

It is clear that the police and criminal justice datasets that are used to develop these systems can lead to discrimination and bias, exacerbating existing inequalities in policing and the criminal legal system. However, there is a larger structural quandary that reinforces power dynamics upheld by law enforcement bodies, that especially impacts racialised people. The introduction of technological tools in the process is one more element in this hierarchical structure.

Transparency and accountability

Finally, it is important to highlight that the lack of transparency in the Spanish territory is leading to the impossibility of independently and properly scrutinising the functioning of these systems. Opacity surrounding the operation of policing and criminal justice automated systems and algorithms is a fundamental bar to justice and accountability, raising questions about the fairness and impartiality of the systems and the processes which they influence.

If people do not know about a system in use by law enforcement or in the criminal legal system that affects them or their case, they are not able to challenge it. This prevents people from seeking redress and upholding and protecting their fundamental rights.

Urgent commitment to transparency, opening up relevant information to the public via a public register of automated decision-making or algorithmic systems in law enforcement and criminal justice is needed. In addition, responding to public information requests on the use and impact of these systems is necessary to foster trust and public scrutiny by impacted individuals, as well as civil society.

¹⁴⁹ Rights International Spain and Open Society Justice Initiative (2019), "Under Suspicion: The Impact of Discriminatory Policing in Spain", Report: <https://www.justiceinitiative.org/uploads/21ac6560-639d-461c-a6b7-06822ad1c07e/under-suspicion-the-impact-of-discriminatory-policing-in-spain-20190924.pdf>; Video: <https://www.justiceinitiative.org/voices/under-suspicion-the-impact-of-discriminatory-policing-in-spain>; Arenas-García I and García-España E, (2022), "Police stop and search in Spain: an overview of its use, impacts and challenges", March 2022, <https://indret.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/1715.pdf>

*This report was produced by Naiara Bellio with the collaboration
of Ana Valdivia & Javier Sánchez Monedero.
Edited by AlgoRace, Griff Ferris & Sofia Lyall.
Translated by Aurora Ali & Najim M. Ouled.
Design and layout by Isabel Muriedas*

The publication of this report was supported by
Statewatch as part of a European project funded by the
European & Society AI Fund.

 STATEWATCH

European
**Artificial Intelligence
& Society Fund**

AlgoRace

(Des)Racializando la IA